

D1.2

**Propagation characteristics and channel models for
RadioWeaves including reflectarrays**

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Abstract:	This deliverable reports on the work performed for task T1.2 focusing on radio channel measurement, characterization and modelling for RadioWeaves (RW). To study channel characteristics of RW in real indoor environments, several measurement campaigns were conducted in Lund and Graz. We used various measurement settings in terms of geometric configurations of array and user equipments (UEs), static/dynamic environments, line-of-sight (LoS)/non-line-of-sight (NLoS) propagation conditions and signal bandwidth, etc, to simulate different RW use cases that are defined in deliverable D1.1.
Keywords:	Channel measurements, channel characteristics, channel modelling, communication and sensing

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Executive Summary

To study channel characteristics of RW in real indoor environments, several measurement campaigns were conducted in Lund and Graz. We used various measurement settings in terms of geometric configurations of array and UEs, static/dynamic environments, LoS/NLoS propagation conditions and signal bandwidth, etc, to simulate different RW use cases that are defined in deliverable D1.1.

RW in the form of large scale antenna arrays can be essentially viewed as a scaled-up version of conventional massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) systems. However, measurements results exhibit several key differences of RW's channel characteristics from massive MIMO systems. For RW user cases, UEs are typically located within the Rayleigh distance of the receiving array, therefore narrowband and plane wave assumptions are no longer fulfilled over the array as shown in the visualization of ultrawideband (UWB) signals, which poses additional challenges for the development of efficient channel estimation algorithms. Different array portions of the RW view differently on the propagation environment which leads to variations on the channel characteristics along the RW. It is firstly observed that the overall received power intensity is non-uniform across the large synthetic array (LSA). If we further zoom into individual propagation components, variation on their power intensities and visibilities across the LSA are also clearly demonstrated with the estimation results of super-resolution algorithm SBL. Same as the deterministic part of the channel. Fading statistics also becomes non-wide sense stationary for RW. Specifically, small-scale fading (SSF) distributions vary over subarrays with different received power intensity. Shadow fading from environment object and human body yields notably different statistics. These non-stationary properties can be potentially exploited to reduce the computational complexity by processing only the most informative measurements, e.g., measurements from power-concentrated subarrays. Furthermore, decentralized and scalable hardware architectures and algorithms are more and more adopted for large scale arrays, where signal processing is performed locally at each subarray and then locate estimates are fused at the central processing unit. To enhance algorithm performance, the deterministic and stochastic channel characteristic discussed above should be essentially considered, but with different emphasis for different applications. Preliminary investigations of the potential of using RW for super-resolution parametric channel estimation, user spatial separability and wireless power transmission have also been performed. It shows that the superior spatial resolution of RW together with wideband or even UWB signals enables high accurate parametric estimation of multipath components (MPCs) that are associated to geometric propagation environment. Besides, the estimated channel condition number and results from maximum ratio transmission (MRT) demonstrate excellent spatial separability of closely located UEs and potential on using RW for wireless power transfer (WPT) even under NLoS propagation conditions with diffracted signals only.

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List of Acronyms

- ACF** autocorrelation function. 60
- AGC** automatic gain control. 21
- AOA** angle-of-arrival. 6
- AOD** angle-of-departure. 6
- AWGN** additive white Gaussian noise. 4
-
- BS** base station. 13
-
- CBSM** correlation-based stochastic model. 59
- CCS** correlative channel sounder. 33
- CDF** cumulative distribution function. VIII, 15
- CP** cyclic prefix. 21
- CSI** channel state information. 61
- CSP** Contact Service Point. 3
-
- DA** data association. 49
- DAC** digital-to-analog converter. 21
- DM** diffuse multipath. 4
-
- END** energy neutral device. 63
-
- FA** federation anchor. 62
- FPGA** field-programmable gate array. 20
-
- GBSM** geometry-based stochastic model. 59
-
- LIS** large intelligent surface. 25
- LoS** line-of-sight. II, 1
- LSA** large synthetic array. II, 1

- LSF** large-scale fading. 14

- MIMO** multiple-input multiple-output. II, 1
- MPC** multipath component. II, 2
- MRC** maximum ratio combining. 25
- MRT** maximum ratio transmission. II, 18

- NLoS** non-line-of-sight. II, 1

- OFDM** orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing. 4

- PDF** probability density function. 59
- PLE** pathloss exponent. 14
- PPS** pulse-per-second. 19

- RA** reflectarray. 60
- Rb** Rubidium. 19
- RCS** radar cross section. VIII, 6
- RF** radio frequency. 19
- RIS** reflective intelligent surface. 60
- RW** RadioWeaves. II, 1

- SBL** sparse Bayesian learning. X, 48
- SISO** single-input single-output. 41
- SMC** specular multipath component. 62
- SNR** signal-to-noise ratio. 18
- SSF** small-scale fading. II, 14

- TDMA** time-division multiple access. 21
- TOA** time-of-arrival. 47
- TOSM** through-open-short-match. 34

- UE** user equipment. II, 1
- ULA** uniform linear array. 48
- URA** uniform rectangular array. X, 43
- USRP** universal software radio peripheral. 19
- UWB** ultrawideband. II, 1

VNA vector network analyzer. 33

VR visibility region. 2

WPT wireless power transfer. II, 2

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Chapter 1

Introduction

With the RadioWeaves (RW) infrastructure being characterized by a wide spatial distribution, different parts of the system can experience fundamentally different propagation conditions, i.e., environments. To explore the full potential of RW for communication, sensing and new intelligent services envisioned for RW, it is of vital importance to have channel models that essentially consider all the key propagation characteristics, yet emphasize differently for different applications, use cases or device classes. This deliverable reports on the work performed for task T1.2 regarding radio channel measurement, characterization and modeling for RW.

Deliverable D1.1 [11] provides initial discussions on channel models for RW-based connectivity based on our previous experience and observations from massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) systems. Of course, the physical propagation channel is the same as for any radio systems in a given frequency band, but there are aspects and details that become more important for this particular system design that have not been studied in detail before, especially with respect to the extremely large array size, the intra element radio channel and bi-static sensing capabilities.

This derivable provides a comprehensive and in-depth study on channel characteristics of RW in real indoor environments based on measurement campaigns conducted in Lund University and TU Graz. We used different settings in terms of geometric configurations of antenna arrays and user equipments (UEs), static/dynamic environments, line-of-sight (LoS)/non-line-of-sight (NLoS) propagation conditions and signal bandwidth, etc, to simulate different RW deployment scenarios and use cases. In Lund, a static channel measurement was performed at a mid-band centered at 5.6 GHz with 240 MHz bandwidth. We emulated an indoor scenario where 16 static UEs communicate with a large synthetic array (LSA) consisting of 15520 elements. Furthermore, to study channel dynamic behavior, radio measurements were also performed with a new multi-link channel sounder built on the National Instruments (NI) Universal Software Radio Peripheral (USRP) hardware with a maximum instantaneous bandwidth of 40 MHz. Measurements in TU Graz were performed in two indoor environments—a medium scale lab room and a large scale corridor, using ultrawideband (UWB) signals with maximum available bandwidth of 6.4 GHz centered at 6.95 GHz. An LSA was formed using a wall-sized 2D positioner and communicates with several distributed static UEs. Apart from the device configurations, two types of measurements are considered: (i) mono-static: RW arrays act as transmitters and receivers for sensing and passive/active communications; (ii) bi-static: RW arrays communicate with UEs that are spatially separated.

The analysis on static measurements provides insights into the non-stationary properties of the

propagation channel across a RW array, in particular the non-uniform distribution of the receive power intensity and variations on fading statistics. With the superior delay and angular resolution due to large signal bandwidth and large array aperture, we further refine the analysis to a single propagation component level. We used a super-resolution parametric channel estimation algorithm—sparse Bayesian learning (SBL)—to obtain multipath component (MPC) parameters such as delay, angle and complex amplitude, and statistical properties of unresolvable (diffuse) MPCs. The results of the SBL algorithm give a straightforward interpretation of the non-uniform amplitude distribution and visibility regions (VRs) of individual MPCs over the array. The analysis on the measurements with dynamic UEs further demonstrate the consistent effects of these channel features/properties over space and time. The observed non-stationary channel properties lead to the new concept “federation” for RW [3], which implies the use of a sub-set of RW resources to support a certain service/class of devices. The analysis on super-resolution channel estimation results also benefits the design of a suitable framework for the environment model, presumably comprising geometric elements (e.g., scatter points and surfaces in the environment), regression models (e.g. to interpolate large-scale properties like visibility and reflection characteristics of objects), and stochastic parts (e.g., for diffuse multipath).

The propagation characteristics that were identified in the measurement campaigns provide important information and new perspectives for the modeling of statistic and stochastic RW propagation channel. When it comes to different RW applications, e.g., communication, positioning or wireless power transfer (WPT), models should focus differently on the description of different channel features.

Apart from the analysis on channel properties, we also performed preliminary investigation on the potential of using RW for spatial separating closely located UEs and WPT under LoS and NLoS propagation conditions.

The structure of the document is summarized as follows:

- Chapter 1 gives an overview on the objective of this deliverable and performed works.
- Chapter 2 reviews the deterministic-stochastic channel models for RW on a theoretic level.
- Chapter 3 presents the measurement campaigns and the corresponding analysis.
- Chapter 4 discusses the insights regarding the channel model that can be derived from the measurement analysis, and considerations on different RW applications.

Chapter 2

Channel Model for RadioWeaves

This chapter introduces the main components of the envisioned channel model for RW on a theoretic level, introducing a suitable deterministic-stochastic channel model and the necessary geometry relations. The class of deterministic-stochastic channels models is widely used in literature [38, 40, 41, 42, 45] as they allow to model environment geometry-based multipath propagation, usually in some form of deterministic signal components, as well as the randomness of the channel by considering diffuse or dense multipath components by means of point source scatterers. We start by formulating a generic signal model and relate this to the different RW structures, considering variable values of measurement/signal bandwidth and geometric configuration of antennas at the infrastructure side, e.g., at the distributed Contact Service Points (CSPs), as well as on the mobile devices communicating with the RW. The channel model is based on the initial channel model described in [11], extending the notion for visibility regions [12] to the deterministic multipath components. With large aperture MIMO systems being of special interest in recent years investigating non-stationary effects [4, 14, 31], a suitable model for multipath propagation needs to account for similar effects as well as spherical wave propagation, e.g., [5, 44].

The signal and system model contain hardware related effects and allows to directly formulate the sampled signals that are the input of various algorithms. These hardware related effects are for example non-ideal antennas, the (measurement) bandwidth limitation of the system but also specific signal waveforms that could be optimized for different applications. The channel model in turn describes propagation between two points in space and includes all environment related aspects, such as amplitude (and phase) changes due to reflection, scattering at objects in the environment, or path loss due to propagation. Ideally, the channel model is independent of any system characteristics, while the implementation efficiency can in general be improved by employing system specific simplifying assumptions.

2.1 Signal and System Model

The CSPs represent the interface between the radio channel and the processing infrastructure of RW. They thus handle all transmission and reception tasks on the hardware/signal level, as well higher as level tasks such as data back-haul, scheduling and possible computation task with low latency requirements [10, 11].

In the signal model we include a deterministic component consisting of a suitable number of specular MPCs, a stochastic component representing scattering and diffuse propagation in the

environment, and additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN). For a single CSP, the sampled received signal \mathbf{y} contains these three parts and is denoted as

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{x}_d(\boldsymbol{\theta}) + \mathbf{w}_s + \mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{C}^{NML} \quad (2.1)$$

where the vector $\mathbf{x}_d(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ denotes the deterministic signal component parameterized by some parameter vector $\boldsymbol{\theta}$, the vector \mathbf{w}_s contains stochastic signal components, and \mathbf{w} the (complex) AWGN modeling receiver noise. The deterministic part $\mathbf{x}_d(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ consists of a (finite) number of propagation paths that can be attributed to specific environment features, e.g., reflective surfaces objects or similar. In realistic environments this number is unknown and varies depending on the locations of the transmitting and receiving devices. The stochastic part can represent any form of stochastic multipath propagation such as scattering [12, 28, 41] or so called a dense multipath component [27, 38, 39]. In (2.1) all signal samples obtained by for example a single CSP are stacked into one vector of dimension NML , where N represents the number of signal samples per antenna, e.g., link or radio channel, M represents the number of antennas at the CSP and L the number of UEs (or UE antennas). The signal can be formulated in either the time- or frequency-domain, giving equivalent representations, whereas algorithms can profit from using a specific domain in terms of performance improvements or from using the same domain as the modulation scheme, e.g., orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing (OFDM), for intuitive understanding.

We consider a CSP at a position $\mathbf{a}_{\text{CSP}} = [a_x, a_y, a_z]^\top$ consisting of M antennas serving L UE devices with the l th UE located at position $\mathbf{p}_{\text{UE}}^{(l)} = [p_x^{(l)}, p_y^{(l)}, p_z^{(l)}]^\top$. At the CSP, the m th antenna element position is denoted as $\mathbf{a}_{\text{CSP}}^{(m)} = [a_x^{(m)}, a_y^{(m)}, a_z^{(m)}]^\top$. We employ a MIMO channel model where the UEs transmit a (complex-valued) baseband signal $s(f)$ with a specified bandwidth B and with the l th element of the transmit signal vector representing the l th UE signal. The signal $\mathbf{y}(f)$ received at the CSP at (baseband) frequency f is denoted by

$$\mathbf{y}(f) = \underbrace{\sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{H}_k(f) \mathbf{s}(f)}_{\text{deterministic}} + \underbrace{\sum_{j=1}^J \mathbf{H}_j^{(\text{sc})}(f) \mathbf{s}(f)}_{\text{stochastic}} + \mathbf{w}(f) \quad (2.2)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times L}$ is the channel matrix of the k th MPC, $\mathbf{H}_j^{(\text{sc})} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times L}$ the channel matrix of the j th scattered path, and $\mathbf{s}(f) = [s_1(f), \dots, s_L(f)]^\top \in \mathbb{C}^L$ the transmit signal vector of the UEs in complex baseband.

The first term in (2.2) models deterministic reflections as a sum of scalar products of the separate channel-matrices for K MPCs, including the LoS. The second term models randomness in the received signals, e.g., by means of point source scatterers and is often termed diffuse multipath (DM). The third term $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{C}^M$ denotes complex AWGN with variance σ_n^2 .

2.2 Channel Model

The following sections describe the models for MPCs and DM in detail, specifying the required channel matrices. With the former modeling specular reflections modeled as rays, the latter models scattering at rough surfaces and/or diffraction.

Figure 2.1: Schematic illustration of the geometry-based channel model. Specular multipath propagation in an exemplary environment is modeled by image CSPs according to an image source model. An exemplary distribution of possible point source scatters are distributed in proximity of the UE device.

2.2.1 Specular Multipath

Deterministic MPCs are modeled according to an image source model [27, 36] based on a geometric environment model, allowing to compute the position $\mathbf{a}_{\text{CSP},k}$ of an image source representing the k th MPC. These components contain position related information and are termed deterministic MPCs. They are related to the environment via a suitable geometric model, using an image source model. The entries of the corresponding channel matrix $\mathbf{H}_k(f)$ can be defined in multiple ways, depending on the application. In this case, we will outline the two most common descriptions, the first focusing on the employed antennas and the second on the underlying position dependent radio channel.

Model for power considerations: Focusing on (what could be termed) a physically correct model for antennas for communications or power transfer, a common definition of the ml th entry of the channel matrix, already employed in [2, 9], is

$$[\mathbf{H}_k(f)]_{m,l} = \underbrace{\sqrt{G_{r,l}} \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{4\pi}}}_{\sqrt{A_l}} \sqrt{G_{t,m}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{4\pi}d_{k,m,l}} g_k g_{k,m,l}^{(\text{pol.})} \exp\left(-j\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}d_{k,m,l}\right) \quad (2.3)$$

where $d_{k,m,l} = \|\mathbf{p}_{\text{UE}}^{(l)} - \mathbf{a}_{\text{CSP},k}^{(m)}\|$ is the Euclidean distance between the transmit antenna $m \in \{1, \dots, M\}$ of the image source k and the l th UE. $G_{t,m} \triangleq G_t(\varphi, \theta)$ and $G_{r,l} \triangleq G_r(\varphi, \theta)$ denote angle-dependent antenna gains of transmit and receive antennas. The first factor in (2.3) models the square root of the aperture $A_l = G_l \frac{\lambda^2}{4\pi}$ of the l th receiving antenna. The third factor models the spread of power over the surface of a sphere with a radius $d_{k,m,l}$. The factor $g_k \in \mathbb{C}$ represents an amplitude gain and phase-shift associated with reflection k , while the term $g_{k,m,l}^{(\text{pol.})}$ models possible polarization losses due to mismatch of the transmit and receive antenna polarization vectors. The polarization loss $g_{k,m,l}^{(\text{pol.})} \in \mathbb{R}^{[0,1]}$ attains 1 in case of perfectly aligned polarization vectors and 0 in case of orthogonal polarization vectors (see [2, Appendix A] for more details). Finally, the

complex exponential term models the phase shift due to the distance $d_{k,m,l}$ traveled, with λ being the wavelength of the transmitted signal in the passband.

When the transmit signal vector \mathbf{s} (omitting the frequency) is given as a vector of complex-valued power waves (with a unit of $\sqrt{\text{power}}$), (2.3) models the Friis transmission equation for power wave amplitudes. Received power P_r and transmitted power P_t then follow the relation

$$\frac{P_r}{P_t} = \frac{\|\mathbf{y}\|^2}{\|\mathbf{s}\|^2} = \text{path gain} \quad (2.4)$$

which corresponds to the RF-to-RF transmission efficiency as used for WPT [2].

Model for channel considerations: When focusing on the channel parameters, i.e., directions and path delays, relevant for positioning applications, it is sensible to express the entries of the channel matrix according to

$$[\mathbf{H}_k(f)]_{m,l} = \mathbf{b}_m^{(\text{rx})}(\varphi_{k,m}^{(\text{rx})}, \theta_{k,m}^{(\text{rx})})^\top \mathbf{A}_{k,m,l}(f) \mathbf{b}_l^{(\text{tx})}(\varphi_{k,l}^{(\text{tx})}, \theta_{k,l}^{(\text{tx})}) \exp(-j2\pi(f + f_c)\tau_{k,m,l}) \quad (2.5)$$

$$= \tilde{\alpha}_{k,m,l} \exp(-j2\pi(f + f_c)\tau_{k,m,l}) \quad (2.6)$$

where $\mathbf{b}_m^{(\text{rx})}(\varphi, \theta) \in \mathbb{C}^2$ and $\mathbf{b}_l^{(\text{tx})}(\varphi, \theta) \in \mathbb{C}^2$ are the polarimetric antenna patterns of the l th and m th array elements as receivers and transmitters respectively. The channel parameters of the k th MPC are included in terms of azimuth and elevation angle-of-arrival (AOA) $\varphi_{k,m}^{(\text{rx})}$ and $\theta_{k,m}^{(\text{rx})}$ and angle-of-departure (AOD) $\varphi_{k,m}^{(\text{tx})}$ and $\theta_{k,m}^{(\text{tx})}$ and propagation time-delay $\tau_{k,m,l}$. Note that when using an image source model, all angles need to be computed with the correct orientation of the image source. The matrix $\mathbf{A}_{k,m,l}(f) \in \mathbb{C}^{2 \times 2}$ contains the complex valued MPC amplitudes $\alpha_{k,m,l}^{(p)}$ in polarimetric form accounting for amplitude and phase changes for different polarizations with $p \in \{\text{hh}, \text{vv}, \text{hv}, \text{vh}\}$.

Comparing (2.5) with (2.3) the direct relation becomes clear as $\tilde{\alpha}_{k,m,l} \propto \sqrt{P_t}/(c\tau_{k,m,l})$. When using the same definition as above, the propagation distance $d_{k,m,l} \triangleq c\tau_{k,m,l} = \|\mathbf{p}_{\text{UE}}^{(l)} - \mathbf{a}_{\text{CSP},k}^{(m)}\|$ of MPC k represents a spherical wave model.

2.2.2 Diffuse Multipath Component

The second term of the channel model in (2.2) represents stochastic scattering at small and/or distributed objects, or surfaces that are rough with respect to the signal wavelength λ [26]. The DM can be modeled as $j \in 1, \dots, J$ clusters, each consisting of I_j point source scatterers at positions $\mathbf{p}_{\text{sc},i}^{(j)} = [x_{\text{sc},i}^{(j)}, y_{\text{sc},i}^{(j)}, z_{\text{sc},i}^{(j)}]^\top$ where all impinging specular waves are re-scattered, assuming single-bounce scattering. The resulting channel matrices for scattering cluster j are defined as

$$\mathbf{H}_j^{(\text{sc})}(f) = \mathbf{H}_j^{(\text{rx})}(f)^\top \Sigma_j^{(\text{sc})}(f) \mathbf{H}_j^{(\text{tx})}(f) \quad (2.7)$$

where $\mathbf{H}_j^{(\text{tx})}(f) \in \mathbb{C}^{I \times L}$ is the transmit scatter channel matrix from the UE to the j th scatterer cluster and $\mathbf{H}_j^{(\text{rx})}(f) \in \mathbb{C}^{I \times M}$ is the receive scatter channel matrix from the scatterers to the M receiving antennas in the CSP. $\Sigma_j^{(\text{sc})}(f)$ is a diagonal matrix containing the radar cross sections (RCSs) of all scatterers on its main diagonal.

The j th clusters diffuse multipath channel matrix in (2.7) consists of three components. (Where possible the cluster index j will be neglected for conciseness.) First, the channel matrix from

Figure 2.2: (a) Schematic illustration how the power transmitted by an antenna m at its origin spreads over the spherical surface. The receiving aperture A_l of another antenna collects a part of the transmitted power. (b) Schematic illustration of how the power signal transmitted by the antenna l at its origin spreads over the spherical surface. At a distance $d_{l,i}$, it impinges on a scatterer i with RCS σ_i . (c) A scatterer i located at the origin of a sphere re-radiates power isotropically. The re-radiated power spreads over the surface of the sphere with radius $d_{i,l}$. At the distance $d_{i,l}$ from the scatterer, it impinges on the receiving aperture A_l .

a UE l to a scatterer i , located at a distance $d_{l,i}$ (schematically depicted in Figure 2.2b). The second component is the matrix $\Sigma^{(\text{sc})} = \text{diag} \{ \sqrt{\sigma_1} \exp(j\phi_1), \dots, \sqrt{\sigma_I} \exp(j\phi_I) \} \in \mathbb{C}^{I \times I}$, a diagonal matrix containing the RCS σ_i of point source scatterer $i \in \{1, \dots, I\}$ and an associated phase-shift ϕ_i on its main diagonal.¹ The third component is the channel matrix representing the re-radiation of the component from the i th scatterer to the m th antenna of the CSP, located at a distance $d_{k,m,i}$ (schematically depicted in Figure 2.2c).

As for the MPC models, also scattering can be formulated with a focus on power considerations or the underlying (random) channel parameters. The corresponding channel matrices for transmitter to scatterer and scatterer to receiver channels are again outlined below (again omitting the cluster index j for readability). Note that these representations are equivalent, but put the focus on different aspects of propagation.

Model for power considerations: The entries of the transmit to scatter channel matrix

$$[\mathbf{H}^{(\text{tx})}(f)]_{i,l} = \sqrt{G_t} \frac{1}{\sqrt{4\pi} d_{i,l}} g_{\text{sc}}^{(\text{pol.})} \exp\left(-j \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} d_{i,l}\right) \quad (2.8)$$

model the power density caused by an isotropic antenna l at a distance $d_{i,l}$ (see Figure 2.2b), where any incurring polarization losses are represented by $g_{\text{sc}}^{(\text{pol.})}$. The entries of the receive scatter channel matrix

$$[\mathbf{H}^{(\text{rx})}(f)]_{i,m} = \underbrace{\sqrt{G_{r,m}} \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{4\pi}}}_{\sqrt{A_m}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{4\pi} d_{i,m}} \exp\left(-j \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} d_{i,m}\right) \quad (2.9)$$

model the power received by the m th antenna of the CSP from a scatterer i (see Figure 2.2c).

When employing the above channel matrices, the scatterer channel matrix in (2.7) represents the bistatic radar range equation for power wave amplitudes. The equation for the path gain (2.4) will then allow to obtain power-correct models transmissions from a UE to the CSP.

¹The possible frequency dependency of the scattering matrix indicated in (2.7) is neglected here for simplicity.

Model for channel considerations: When putting the focus on the position related channel parameters, the entries of the channel matrix from transmitter to the scatterers can be denoted as

$$[\mathbf{H}^{(\text{tx})}(f)]_{i,l} = \mathbf{b}_i^{(\text{sc})}(\varphi_{i,l}^{(\text{sc})}, \vartheta_{i,l}^{(\text{sc})})^\top \mathbf{A}_{i,l}(f) \mathbf{b}_l^{(\text{tx})}(\varphi_{i,l}^{(\text{tx})}, \vartheta_{i,l}^{(\text{tx})}) \exp(-j2\pi(f + f_c)\tau_{i,l}) \quad (2.10)$$

$$= \tilde{b}_{i,l}^{(\text{tx})} \exp(-j2\pi(f + f_c)\tau_{i,l}) \quad (2.11)$$

and from scatterers to the receive array by

$$[\mathbf{H}_j^{(\text{rx})}(f)]_{i,m} = \mathbf{b}_m^{(\text{rx})}(\varphi_{j,i,m}^{(\text{rx})}, \vartheta_{j,i,m}^{(\text{rx})})^\top \mathbf{A}_j(f) \mathbf{b}_i^{(\text{sc})}(\varphi_{i,m}^{(\text{sc})}, \vartheta_{i,m}^{(\text{sc})}) \exp(-j2\pi(f + f_c)\tau_{j,i,m}) \quad (2.12)$$

$$= \tilde{b}_{j,i,m}^{(\text{rx})} \exp(-j2\pi(f + f_c)\tau_{j,i,m}). \quad (2.13)$$

In Summary, the latter description puts the focus on the propagation parameters of the MPCs, in this case via the scattered components. As before, both the physical model and parametric models can be related by chosen the parameters correspondingly.

Chapter 3

Propagation Measurements

This chapter introduces the measurement campaigns conducted to investigate and determine key propagation characteristics that affect the RW system. The key propagation characteristics are then used to formulate the channel model in Chapter 4. Table 3.1 briefly summarizes the measurement setups and the environment. More details about each measurement and the corresponding analysis are provided in the following subsections.

mea. campaign	system parameters	environment and UE setups
<i>“wideband synthetic array mea.”</i>	center freq.: 5.6 GHz max. BW: 240 MHz one 3D planar array with dual-polarized patch elements array dim.: 3.4 m × 8.8 m × 1.5 m num. of array elements: 15520	a medium size lab with approx. size 5.95 m × 15.23 m × 2.8 m LoS and NLoS conditions 16 static single-antenna UEs
<i>“dynamic RW mea.”</i>	center freq.: 5.6 GHz max. BW: 40 MHz 6 distributed arrays, each with 4 dual-polarized patch elements num. of array elements: 4 × 6	a medium size lab with approx. size 5.95 m × 15.23 m × 2.8 m LoS and NLoS conditions one dynamic UE
<i>“UWB synthetic array mea.”</i> medium size environment	center freq.: 6.95 GHz max. BW: 3.5 GHz one 2D planar array with vertical-polarized patch elements array dim.: 2.5 m × 1.5 m num. of array elements: 3200	a medium size lab with approx. size 8 m × 6 m × 3 m LoS and NLoS conditions static and synthetically dynamic UEs
<i>“UWB synthetic array mea.”</i> large size environment	center freq.: 6.95 GHz max. BW: 3.5 GHz two 2D planar arrays with vertical-polarized patch elements array dim.: 2.26 m × 1.55 m num. of array elements: 3200	a large size corridor with approx. size 40 m × 10 m × 4 m LoS and NLoS conditions static and synthetically dynamic UEs

Table 3.1: A brief overview of the performed measurement campaigns, the corresponding setup and environment.

3.1 Wideband Synthetic Array Measurements

The concept of RW has been proposed in recent years and generically refers to a large electromagnetic surface that actively transmits and receives electromagnetic fields [19]. A feasible implementation of RW is using a very large number of antennas to form a large scale array. Thus, a discrete implemented RW can be essentially viewed as a scaled-up version of massive MIMO, which has much larger array aperture therefore much higher directivity and spatial multiplexing capability. Discrete RWs have been proven to be no different than continuous surface in terms of achievable performance such as capacity [19]. Most of the RW-related research works, e.g., system design and performance analysis, are built on theoretical channel models and emulated radio measurements. To study the channel characteristics of RW in real propagation environments, a LSA was formed in the 5G lab at Lund University, and real radio measurements were collected given different UE configurations representing various use cases. In the following sections, we first introduce the measurement setups, and then analyze the fading statistics and non-stationary properties of the radio channel. Furthermore, some preliminary investigation on the user separability and wireless power transfer performance are presented.

3.1.1 Measurement Environment and Devices

As shown in Figure 3.1a, the lab room (dimension 5.95 m \times 15.23 m \times 2.8 m) is a scattering-rich environment with the presence of light tube fixings and Cooling/ventilation ducts on the ceiling, and the furniture, equipment and coated windows along the wall. The room floor plan is demonstrated in Figure 3.1b.

A measurement campaign was performed using the RUSK LUND channel sounder (Figure 3.2a), which is designed for measuring the frequency transfer functions in the 300 MHz, 2 GHz, and 5 GHz frequency bands with a bandwidth up to 240 MHz. The channel sounder uses the switched array principle to perform MIMO measurements, which sequentially swipe through all the transmit and receive antenna pairs. Furthermore, it uses a multi-tone, OFDM-like signal to ensure a constant power spectral density over the whole bandwidth. The wideband LSA measurement campaign was conducted over a 240 MHz bandwidth centered at 5.6 GHz. At the transmitter side, 16 monopole antennas (BJTEK MA-2458) (Figure 3.2c) were used as 16 static single-antenna UEs with a transmit power of 27 dBm. The UE antenna has a quasi-omnidirectional radiation pattern on the azimuth plane, and its vertical peak gain direction is slightly elevated. At the receiver side, a 3D LSA was formed using a vertical linear array and a wheel sensor (Figure 3.2b). Specifically, the linear array with 32 dual-polarized patch elements was mounted on a trolley as shown in Figure 3.2a and manually moved along a predefined L-shape trajectory at a very low speed. The measurement of the uplink signal from UEs to the linear array is triggered by the transistor-transistor logic (TTL) signal of the wheel sensor after every 2.513 cm of movement (approximately half a wavelength), therefore the horizontal spacing distance between array elements is half a wavelength.

(a) 5G lab, E-huset, Lund University, Sweden

(b) Floor plan of the 5G lab

Figure 3.1: The indoor measurement environment.

(a) RUSK LUND channel sounder

(b) wheel sensor

(c) monopole antenna

Figure 3.2: Measurement equipment.

As shown in Figure 3.3, the 3D LSA (dimension $3.4 \text{ m} \times 8.8 \text{ m} \times 1.5 \text{ m}$) consists of two mutually perpendicular synthetic planar arrays (part-1 and part-2), where part-1 consists of $350 \times 32 = 11200$ patch elements and part-2 consists of $135 \times 32 = 4320$ patch elements, so the LSA contains a total of 15520 elements.

Figure 3.3: Floor plan of the measurement environment, the 3D LSA formed by moving a vertical linear array, and different setups of UE locations.

3.1.2 UE Setups

To investigate the channel characteristics under different use cases, e.g., closely-located or distributed UEs, LoS or NLoS propagation condition, we use 5 different setups of UE locations in the measurement as shown in the floor plan (Figure 3.3) and the pictures in Figure 3.4:

- **“parallel”**: 16 UEs with interval distance of 2λ form a linear array that is parallel to part-1, and LoS propagation condition applies.
- **“perpendicular”**: 16 UEs with interval distance of 2λ form a linear array which is perpendicular to part-1, LoS propagation condition applies.
- **“dense random”**: UEs were “randomly” placed in a small area, LoS condition applies.
- **“body shadowing”**: UEs surround a water-filled phantom, which simulates body shadowing effect and human rotation.
- **“wide spread”**: UEs widely distribute in the lab, and a metal shelf full of books acts as a shadowing object.

UEs antennas are located 0.65 m above the ground in the first four setups and 0.61 m in the “wide spread” setup, which are slightly above the lower edge (0.57 m above the ground) of the virtual 3D LSA.

Figure 3.4: Pictures show 5 different UE setups.

3.1.3 Measurement Results and Analysis

Power distribution

Figure 3.5 shows the power distribution across the 3D LSA based on the measured signals from the 3rd and 15th UEs of setup "wide spread". High power intensity is observed on the sub-arrays close to the UEs and maximum 60 dB power variation is observed across the array. The non-uniform power distribution can be explained as follows. When the dimension of the antenna array becomes very large and the distances between the base station (BS), UEs and scatterers are smaller than the Rayleigh distance (i.e., near-field propagation), different array portions view differently on the propagation environment. Each propagation path may experience notably difference on the path loss across array elements due to different propagation distances and antenna gain. Moreover, propagation paths may only be visible from a portion of the array due to shadowing from environment objects or human body. Therefore, received power from each UE may vary

Figure 3.5: Received power over the 3D LSA given the measured signal from the (a) 3rd UE and the (b) 15th UE of setup “wide spread”. The UE position is marked with a pink “x”. The black dashed lines denote the projection of UE coordinates on the LSA.

significantly across array elements. The spatial non-stationary property can be potentially exploited to reduce the computational complexity of algorithms, e.g., parametric channel estimation or localization, by processing only the measurement data from power-concentrated subarrays.

Fading Statistics

Fading statistics is of great importance for the design of radio channel models and radio systems. The rapid fluctuation of the received amplitudes happening within a small spatial scale (of a few wavelengths) is called small-scale fading (SSF). The fluctuation is caused by the destructive and constructive superposition of different MPCs. The small-scale averaged amplitude over each small spatial area typically varies over a larger spatial scale (tens to a few hundred wavelengths) due to shadowing by environment objects or human body, i.e., large-scale fading (LSF). In this section, we analyze the SSF and LSF statistics by collectively analyzing the measurements of all 16 UEs of setups “body shadowing” and “wide spread”, respectively.

Figure 3.6a and Figure 3.6b show the received signal power, free-space channel gain, small-scaled averaged signal power and the averaged channel gain. For setup “wide spread” where UEs are widely distributed over the lab room, larger variations of the distance and distance-dependent pathloss are observed, and the pathloss exponent (PLE) estimated using a linear unbiased estimator [22] is 2.5. The estimated PLE for setup “body shadowing” is slightly larger,

Figure 3.6: Fading statistics. The received signal power, free-space channel gain, small-scaled averaged signal power and averaged channel gain for setup “*body shadowing*” (a) and “*wide spread*” (b). The x -axis denotes the distance from the UE to each LSA element. (c) shows the empirical CDFs of the shadowing loss and their respective fitted Gaussian distributions.

which is 3. For setup “*body shadowing*”, UEs are in very close proximity to the water-filled phantom, thus transmit signal is largely shadowed leading to a larger estimated PLE which is 3.3. Figure 3.6c shows the cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) of shadow fadings. It can be seen that the LSFs for both setups are well described by Gaussian distributions, but the difference between the fading statistics due to body shadowing and environment object shadowing are notable.

We further study the small-scale amplitude statistics. To get insights into the non-stationary property of the SSF over RW, the 3D LSA is segmented into 18 subarrays, each with a physical size of $1.3\text{ m} \times 1.2\text{ m}$. The empirical CDFs of small-scale amplitudes for each subarray and their fitting statistical distributions (Rayleigh, Rician and Gamma) are shown in Figure 3.7 and Figure 3.8 for the 3rd UE and 15th UE of setup “*wide spread*”, respectively. According to the non-stationary power distribution shown in Figure 3.5a and Figure 3.5b, the indexes of power concentrated subarrays are highlighted with red color. For subarrays that are distant from the UE, small-scale amplitudes are well described by Rayleigh distributions, or Rician distributions with very small K factors. This lack of strong Rician channel observation is contrary to the fact that LoS propagation condition applies to most of the subarrays. Given the presence of many highly reflective scatters in the small measurement environment, most of specular MPCs are compact in

Figure 3.7: SSF statistics of different subarrays for the 3rd UE of setup “wide spread”. According to the non-stationary power distribution shown in Figure 3.5a, the indexes of power concentrated subarrays are highlighted with red color.

the delay domain and have amplitudes comparable to that of the LoS path. Furthermore, directive radiation pattern of UE antenna leads to low antenna gain in the direction to some subarrays. For these power-concentrated subarrays, small-scale amplitudes are poorly interpreted by either Rayleigh or Rician distributions, while Gamma distributions yield a better fit.

UE Spatial Separability

In this section, we investigate the potential of RW on spatially separating closely located UEs, and use channel condition number as the indication of the degree of mutual orthogonality among UE signals[13]. For setups “parallel” and “perpendicular”, we select four equally spaced UEs and the measurement matrix is given as $\mathbf{H}_s = [\mathbf{h}_{s,1}, \dots, \mathbf{h}_{s,U}]$ where $\mathbf{h}_{s,u}$ denotes the normalized channel measurements of the u th UE and s th setup. The channel condition number κ is obtained as the ratio between the maximum and minimum singular values of \mathbf{H}_s , i.e.,

$$\kappa = \frac{\sigma_{\max}}{\sigma_{\min}}. \quad (3.1)$$

Figure 3.8: SSF statistics of different subarrays for the 15th UE of setup “wide spread”. According to the non-stationary power distribution shown in Figure 3.5b, the indexes of power concentrated subarrays are highlighted with red color.

Clearly, $\kappa \in [1, \infty)$, and a small value close to 1 indicates a better spatial separability and higher achievable sum-rate given fixed transmit energy [32].

It has been shown in previous works [13] with real channel measurements that massive MIMO may provide unsatisfactory performance on the UE spatial separation if the channels to different UEs are highly correlated in conditions like LoS. However, when the array scale is further increased to the level of RW, spatial separability can be greatly improved in these challenging situations. Figure 3.9 shows the channel condition numbers given different UE spacing distances $\{0.12, 0.24, 0.36, 0.48, 0.6\}$ m and different polarimetric transmission schemes. In general, the result implies the excellent UE spatial separability of the 3D LSA even for the smallest UE spacing, and this is made possible by the large array aperture providing high spatial resolution and the spreading scatters which help to decorrelate channels to different UEs. It is observed that the channel condition number for “parallel” setup is smaller than that of “perpendicular” setup, which can be explained by the fact that the UEs of “parallel” setup benefit from the larger aperture of the part-1 then the UEs of “perpendicular” setup from part-2. Moreover, different polarimetric transmissions make no major difference on the separability.

Figure 3.9: Channel condition numbers. The notations $\{v2v, v2h, v2dual\}$ denote different polarimetric transmission from the UE to array elements, as for example v2h represents the vertical-to-horizontal transmission, and v2dual represents the vertical-to-(horizontal & vertical transmission).

Maximum Ratio Transmission

Wireless power transmission is one of the promising applications of RW. The large array aperture of discrete RW helps to form very narrow beams to the targeted UEs, i.e., maximize the power density at the target UE and minimize power dispersion to nearby UEs. The maximum ratio transmission (MRT) scheme [30] (also known as conjugate beamforming) which maximizes the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) at the UE side is used to perform a preliminary evaluation on the wireless power transmission capability of RW. Figure 3.10 shows the MRT coefficients for “parallel” and “perpendicular” UE setups and 2D RW (part-1 only) and 3D RW (part-1 and part-2). The amplitude of the surf plots can be approximately interpreted as the power density at the j th UE’s position when performing MRT transmission to the i th UE. Intuitively, the higher the concentration of power on the diagonal, the better the power transfer capability. When 2D RW is used as shown in Figure 3.10a and Figure 3.10b, the 2D RW shows better capability on focusing power to the target UE for “parallel” setup than “perpendicular”, which can be easily explained by the large array aperture along y -axis. The 3D RW further extends the array aperture along x -axis, therefore, major improvement can be observed for “perpendicular” setup, as shown in Figure 3.10b and Figure 3.10d.

Figure 3.10: MRT power levels of 16 UEs for setups “parallel” and “perpendicular”.

3.2 Dynamic Radioweave Measurements

3.2.1 Measurement Environment and Devices

The environment is the same as described in Sec. 3.1.1. The RUSK channel sounder measures a virtual array to investigate a large synthetic array and can therefore not capture dynamic properties where the UE may be moving around. To enable measurements of the channel’s dynamic behavior, a subset of the RW were selected; see Figure 3.13. In our case, the subset is limited by the available equipment (described below).

The radio measurements were performed with a new multi-link channel sounder developed at Lund University. The system is built around the National Instruments (NI) universal software radio peripheral (USRP) hardware. More specifically, the NI-USRP 2953 platform. Each USRP connects to an external Rubidium (Rb) oscillator, which provides a 10 MHz reference frequency and a pulse-per-second (PPS) to align the snapshots in the distributed system. Before each measurement campaign, one of the Rubidium oscillators is selected as the primary and is used to align the PPS signal on the others. The USRP consists of two radio frequency (RF) boards with an analog bandwidth of 40 MHz and a tuneable carrier frequency between 1.2-6 GHz. Henceforth, a *radio* refers to *one* of these boards – i.e one USRP consists of two radios. The NI LabVIEW 2021 software framework is used on the host computers to configure the radios and to acquire and store data.

(a) Long side

(b) Short side

(c) Overview, with shelf present

Figure 3.11: Pictures showing the room setup. In the photographs the obstructing shelf is shown.

The sounder can transmit any desired waveform which gets loaded onto the memory of the field-programmable gate array (FPGA). During these measurements the Zadoff-Chu sequence was used and distributed on the carriers of an OFDM-like symbol. The symbol can be repeated

arbitrary number of times which can be useful to add a cyclic prefix (CP).

The system is based on a time-division multiple access (TDMA) which assigns all participant radios a unique time-slot to transmit. All other radios in the setup receive and store the captured complex samples during the transmission slot. When a radio is active it was set to transmit 4 repetitions of the signal. The first is used as CP and the rest can be used for averaging to increase the SNR. We define the snapshot time T_S as the time it takes for all radios to transmit their sounding signal s . If we have N radios, each transmitting T_{sig} seconds, then the snapshot time becomes $T \Rightarrow T_S = T_{\text{sig}} \cdot N$ long. In the presented work, one of the time-slots is allocated for the UE, while the rest are part of the RW. The snapshot repetition rate f_{rep} is the number of snapshots sent within a second. The repetition rate sets the resolvable Doppler, while the length of s relates to the maximum excess delay of the channel.

Since two consecutive time-slots in the TDMA scheme can have radically different signal amplitudes due to the spatial distribution of the RW in the room, an automatic gain control (AGC) had to be implemented. The AGC had to be able to set the gain faster than the expected maximum excess delay of the channel — which was achieved by implementing it on the FPGA.

The same antenna elements as in the WB Synthetic Array measurements were used. That is, on the RW side directive patch antennas and on the UE an omnidirectional monopole on a ground plane. The OFDM symbols were 512 sub-carriers long, where 449 of them were active which resulted in a measured bandwidth of 35 MHz, centered around 5.6 GHz. The carriers at the edges and the DC component were nulled. This will of course have as a consequence that the Zadoff-Chu sequence will no longer have unit amplitude. This was taken care of by not using the full range of the digital-to-analog converter (DAC) to avoid non-linearity. Defining the crest factor of the signal as in (3.2) and using a Zadoff-Chu sequence with parameters given by Table 3.2 gives $C_{\text{crest}} \approx 1.34$.

$$C_{\text{crest}} = \frac{\max(s(t))}{\sqrt{1/n \sum_0^{n-1} s(t)^2}} \quad (3.2)$$

Figure 3.12: Pictures showing some of the equipment used.

To summarize, the system during this measurement campaign consists of the following hardware:

- 7 NI-USRP 2953r, 40 MHz bandwidth, Figure 3.12c.
- 3 SRS FS725, 10 MHz Rb frequency standard.
- 1 SRS FS740, 10 MHz Rb frequency standard with GNSS, Figure 3.12b.
- 7 Host computers to control the radios, and for logging measurement data.
- 1 Modified hoverboard, controllable over Bluetooth (2.4 GHz), Figure 3.12e.
- 12 Patch antennas (6 pairs), Figure 3.12a.
- 1 Monopole antenna on a ground plane, Figure 3.2c.

3.2.2 Measured Scenarios

Four different scenarios were measured to investigate the channel properties. Two scenarios (Scenarios 1a and 1b) used a modified hoverboard with a measurement device on top of it, acting as a mobile user. In the other two (Scenarios 2a and 2b), all radios were static, and a person was walking in the environment instead. The environment is depicted in Figure 3.11 and Figure 3.13.

- 1a** Mobile UE along a trajectory **with** a shelf in the environment.
- 1b** Mobile UE along a trajectory **without** a shelf in the environment.
- 2a** Person along a trajectory **with** a shelf in the environment.
- 2b** Person along a trajectory **without** a shelf in the environment.

In **Scenario 1**, the mobile UE was driving along a given trajectory. The UE's direction and speed were manually controlled with a game controller over Bluetooth. The speed was limited to 1 m/s, with a carrier frequency of 5.6 GHz, giving a maximum Doppler of approximately 18 Hz.

The difference between 1a and 1b is the presence or absence of a shelf in the environment, respectively.

Figure 3.13: Dynamic RW measurement scenarios.

In contrast to Scenario 1, in **Scenario 2** the UE did not move, but a person walked along the trajectory, trying to keep a constant speed of approximately 1m/s, which should lead to similar Doppler shifts as in Scenario 1.

The difference between Scenario 2a and 2b is the presence or absence of a shelf in the environment.

Given the room dimensions, selected carrier frequency, and mobility of the moving objects, the measurement parameters were chosen according to Table 3.2.

Table 3.2: System parameters during measurements.

Parameter	Value
carrier frequency	5.6 GHz
sounding length	12.8 μ s
active sub-carriers	449
sub-carrier spacing	78.125 kHz
bandwidth	35.078125 MHz
signal repetitions	4
total signal length	51.2 μ s
number of radios	13
snapshot length	665.6 μ s
repetition rate, f_{rep}	200 Hz (5 ms)
max. resolvable Doppler frequency	100 Hz
max. resolvable velocity	5 m/s
tx power	\approx 11 dBm (with minor variations)
measurement time per scenario	29 s

There are in total 13 antennas (radios) in the measured scenarios; 12 are along the RW and the last one is on the robot acting as the mobile UE. The antennas are polarized as described in Table 3.3. The antenna positions are shown in Figure 3.14.

Table 3.3: Antennas used — and their polarizations.

Antenna ID	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
Antenna type	Patch					...						Patch	Monopole
Polarization	H	V	V	H	H	V	V	V	V	H	H	V	V

Figure 3.14: Overview of antenna placement in RW, and position of UE.

3.2.3 Measurement Results and Analysis

The system saves and logs the channel impulse response from each antenna, and at repetition rate f_{rep} . Each participating radio in the system saves $\mathbf{h}(l, s, \tau)$, where l is current radio in the snapshot, s is the snapshot index, and τ is the delay. An FFT is performed in the last dimension to get the channel transfer function, $\mathbf{H}(l, s, f)$. Both \mathbf{h} and \mathbf{H} are complex-valued.

To get the small-scale averaged channel power, snapshots within approximately 10 wavelengths are averaged. At 5.9 GHz the wavelength is approximately 0.054 m. Moving at 1 m/s leads to an averaging window of around 0.5 m – or every 0.5 seconds. The instantaneous amplitude, $A_{l,s}$, for each channel link l and at each snapshot s along the trajectory is calculated as

$$A_{l,s} = \sum_{i=0}^{N_f-1} |H_{l,s,i}| \quad (3.3)$$

Then the small-scale averaged (SSA) amplitude $\{A_{l,s_k}^{SSA}\}_{s_k=0}^{N_s-m+1}$, with an window size of m , becomes (assuming m even)

$$A_{l,s_k}^{SSA} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=s_k-m/2}^{s_k+m/2-1} A_{l,i}, \quad s_k \in [m/2, N_s - m/2 - 1]. \quad (3.4)$$

RMS Delay Spread

Due to the bandwidth being limited to 35 MHz, most of the power were captured within in the first delay tap. In some of the links a small second tap could be seen. Table 3.4 shows the RMS Delay spread for the four measurement scenarios. In Scenario 1 the results are presented as seen from the UE (radio 13). In Scenario 2 radio 5 has been chosen as a representative of the results.

Table 3.4: Representative RMS Delay Spread for Scenarios 1 and 2.

RMS Delay Spread (ns)					
Link (TX,RX)	Scenario 1a	Scenario 1b	Link (TX,RX)	Scenario 2a	Scenario 2b
(1,13)	119.03	119.28	(1,5)	128.61	129.05
(2,13)	115.81	118.57	(2,5)	123.33	128.99
(3,13)	117.40	118.78	(3,5)	120.81	118.41
(4,13)	119.06	119.94	(4,5)	119.96	119.77
(5,13)	115.78	118.03	(5,5)	-	-
(6,13)	115.93	118.38	(6,5)	-	-
(7,13)	117.42	119.31	(7,5)	129.97	123.77
(8,13)	117.34	119.64	(8,5)	121.86	123.14
(9,13)	115.38	120.98	(9,5)	128.49	129.88
(10,13)	121.43	121.35	(10,5)	117.46	129.95
(11,13)	119.99	123.80	(11,5)	115.02	113.63
(12,13)	114.78	121.62	(12,5)	121.33	124.25
(13,13)	-	-	(13,5)	118.36	119.04
Mean	117.81	120.69	Mean	122.29	123.62
Std. Dev.	2.28	2.93	Std. Dev.	4.66	5.23

Power distribution - Mobile UE

From the measurements it is clearly seen how the power moves along the large intelligent surface (LIS) with the UE. The presence of the shelf in the environment can most clearly be seen on e.g. the link where radio 9 is transmitting and radio 13, UE, is listening. Compare link (9,13) in Figures 3.18 and 3.16. At the start of the trajectory the LOS is obstructed and a decrease in received power of around 10 dB can be observed in the first 10 seconds. Using maximum ratio combining (MRC) it is clear that the fading dips do not get as deep.

Figure 3.15: Received power levels, Scenario 1a. In the legend the links are denoted as (TX,RX).

Figure 3.16: Received power levels, Scenario 1a. Small-scale averaged. In the legend the links are denoted as (TX,RX).

Figure 3.17: Received power levels, Scenario 1b. In the legend the links are denoted as (TX,RX).

Figure 3.18: Received power levels, Scenario 1b. Small-scale averaged. In the legend the links are denoted as (TX,RX).

Power distribution - Sensing

In this scenario a person is walking along the trajectory and the UE radio is fixed. There are many links available, and radios 1 and 5, along the RW, have been chosen to illustrate the results. We show the radio channels observed at the location of radio 1 when all others are transmitting at radio 5 when all others are transmitting. In the beginning and the end of the measurements it is clear from Figures 3.19-3.24 that the environment is static. Any variation comes from people in the room. The person was walking at approximately constant speed and it is obvious when the body was obstructing the LOS component. The purpose of the measurements in Scenario 2 is for future further evaluations of a sensing application.

Figure 3.19: Received power levels, Scenario 2a, without shelf. Radio 1 is receiving.

Figure 3.20: Received power levels, Scenario 2a, without shelf. Radio 1 is receiving. Small-scale averaged signal.

Figure 3.21: Received power levels, Scenario 2a, without shelf. Radio 5 is receiving.

Figure 3.22: Received power levels, Scenario 2a, without shelf. Radio 5 is receiving. Small-scale averaged signal.

Figure 3.23: Received power levels, Scenario 2b, with shelf. Radio 5 is receiving.

Figure 3.24: Received power levels, Scenario 2b, with shelf. Radio 5 is receiving. Small-scale averaged signal.

Fading statistics

The figures in previous sections present the small-scale averaged channels. Using this data to extract the fading statistics of the small-scale fading process is presented in this section. The data appears to be spatially non-stationary due to the size/separation of the RW — different links in the system see different channels. Hence the data is not spatially wide-sense stationary. The channel statistics have been done over the whole traveled trajectory, and due to the directivity of the patch antennas, the channel may sometimes be more Rayleigh than Ricean. Hence, the distribution over the whole trajectory is a mixture of LOS and NLOS. The Gamma distribution has the best fit in the majority of the measurements and should therefore be used when modelling.

Figure 3.25: Small-scale fading over the different links to the UE (radio 13). Scenario 1a.

Figure 3.26: Small-scale fading over the different links to the UE (radio 13). Scenario 1b.

Comparing scenarios 1 and 2 it is clear that when all radios are static the amplitude variations are not large. This seems reasonable since the person walking is small in comparison and will not affect the SSF much. It is also quite clear that the Rayleigh distribution is not the best fit in this environment in general, due to all the LOS components. Further detailed characterization is needed to completely model the statistics since it is spatially non wide-sense stationary.

Figure 3.27: Small-scale fading over the different links to radio 5. Scenario 2a.

Figure 3.28: Small-scale fading over the different links to radio 5. Scenario 2b.

3.3 Ultrawideband Synthetic Array Measurements

This section outlines the UWB measurements that were conducted in Graz at Graz University of Technology. All measurements target the analysis of the application of (deterministic) multipath propagation models to LSAs. To this end, a measurement systems was developed, planned and assembled, which enables to perform measurements of *synthetic* LSAs by moving a single antenna along predefined positions of the array and performing all analysis steps in post-processing

after collecting the data. While this type of measurement system allows to measure arbitrary array geometries without the necessity of extensive calibration of the antennas and receive/transmit channels, the investigated environment needs to remain stationary during each measurement run.

We start by introducing the measurement system (RF hardware, mechanical positioner and antennas), followed by a brief description of the measurement environments that were used to collect data, and a short summary of the parameters of the conducted measurements.

3.3.1 Measurement System

The measurement system for synthetic LSAs consists of a mechanical positioner with the channel measurements performed either using a correlative channel sounder (CCS) performing time-domain measurements or using a vector network analyzer (VNA) and performing measurements in the frequency domain. While RW is expected to cover only a relatively small bandwidth with an envisioned system bandwidth of up to 100 MHz (available at different center frequencies), UWB measurements give valuable insight due to the high time resolution, especially when paired with the flexibility and large spatial resolution of the synthetic LSA measurement setup.

Mechanical Positioning Devices

The use of mechanical positioners enables flexible measurements of different array geometries in an automated manner with accurate relative positions between measurement points. This allows to perform measurements of LSAs covering a large area, e.g., exhibiting a large aperture.

Two similar mechanical positioners were constructed, with the dimensions of the employed motion axis allowing to measure roughly $2.5 \text{ m} \times 1.5 \text{ m}$, shown in Figure 3.29a. The vertical motion axis and the horizontal axis A are equipped with *dryve*[®] D1 motor controller driving *dylin*[®] NEMA24 stepper motors allowing accurate positioning in the sub-millimeter range with high repeatability. The horizontal axis B is connected to axis A via a spindle shaft that reduces the load on the motor and allows smooth motion of the vertical axis. The stepper motors feature a holding break to keep the position during stop intervals, and allow motion with variable acceleration, deceleration and velocity. The vertical is equipped with the sledge on which the antennas (or other measurement devices) are be mounted.

To emulate a RW CSP mounted directly on a surface, each mechanical positioner is equipped with a broadband absorber and a reflector plate on the sledge behind the antenna, effectively removing the surface reflection on which the positioner is mounted on. The suppression of the back reflection results in realistic measurements of a CSP equipped with an array mounted directly on an environment surface as described [11]. Due to this construction, the distance from the antenna phase center to the back wall is roughly 43 cm (including the antenna length of 10 cm), i.e., the corresponding RW CSP is not mounted directly on the wall but as close as possible. Depending on how the mechanical positioners are mounted in the environment, the effectively usable measurement area can be smaller due to requirements for safety margins accounting for the size of the absorber and reflector plate.

Radio Measurement Devices

Two different devices are available to perform the radio measurements: a VNA ZVA24 and an *Ilmsens* CCS, where the former performs measurements in the frequency-domain and the lat-

(a) wall mounted mechanical positioner

(b) antenna, absorber and measurement device

(c) antenna and absorber

(d) patch antennas

(e) dipole antennas

Figure 3.29: Measurement setup showing one mechanical positioner mounted on the wall (a) and the corresponding setup consisting of the measurement device, antenna, cables and absorber on reflection plate in (b) and (c). The patch antennas are shown in (d), the dipole antennas in (e).

ter in the time-domain. The VNA covers a frequency range of 24 GHz (from DC) and can be calibrated with a corresponding calibration kit provided with the device. The calibration is a standard through-open-short-match (TOSM) calibration performed for all required measured ports. The CCS covers a frequency band of $f = 3.8 - 10.2$ GHz, centered at a carrier frequency of $f_c = 6.95$ GHz, and allows fully coherent measurements of two receive channels with respect to one transmit channel. To remove the effects of the system response, e.g., cables and internal hardware and cross talk between the two receive channels, a calibration procedure comparable to a TOSM calibration is performed before each measurement. Independent of the used measurement device, all measurements are fully coherent.

UWB Antennas

The antennas that were used in the measurements are dipole antennas and dipole-slot antennas, see Figure 3.29d and Figure 3.29e, with the latter being termed slot antenna for better differentiation. The dipole-slot antennas were manufactured according to the XETS-antenna design from [6], which perform well in the frequency band of interest that selected as 3-10 GHz. While the

VNA covers a much wider frequency region, measurements are only performed in the frequency band for which the antennas are designed. As the measurement aperture will allow reception from azimuth and elevation, the slot antennas' design were chosen as it exhibits an approximately omnidirectional pattern. When mounted on the absorber and reflector plate construction the antennas only receive from the half plane facing away from the absorber, i.e., only in the half plane facing away from the surface the CSP would be mounted on. The antenna gain patterns are shown in Figure 3.30 for the frequency band of interest.

The dipole antennas are made from 2-cent coins and exhibit an omnidirectional pattern in the horizontal plane with increasing attenuation towards nadir and zenith. The cent-antennas were already used in measurements [23, 33] and are known to work well. They are circularly polarized.

The slot antennas were manufactured at TU Graz based on an antenna design proposed in literature [6], termed XETS antennas. Figure 3.30 shows the measured XETS antenna gain pattern for the frequency spectrum of interest. The measurements were performed by TU Vienna in an antenna measurement chamber, characterizing the antenna and absorber-plus-reflector construction jointly. For the gain pattern measurements, the antenna look direction pointed towards 0 deg elevation, e.g., towards the ceiling. The resulting attenuation towards the back, e.g., towards the floor or the wall the mechanical positioner will be mounted on, is clearly visible in all subplots. When mounted on the mechanical positioner as indicated in Figure 3.29, the elevation plane of 90 deg is parallel to the wall and the an elevation angle of 0 deg is perpendicular to the wall, pointing into the environment. The patch antennas are vertically polarized, which needs to be considered manually during the assembly.

3.3.2 Measurement Environments

The UWB measurements were performed in two environments that are applicable to a wide range of the use-cases envisioned for RW and allow to analyze important propagation characteristics that will be encountered in these use-cases. This could for example covers shadowing in the context of tracking of goods or in an electronic labelling scenario in stores, where shelves introduce scattering and obstructions, but is of interest in all environments where multipath propagation can be encountered, which is the case in all use cases. Both environments are indoors, with the first representing a medium size room representative of, e.g., office spaces, assisted living or laboratory environments, and the second being a large size environment representative of, e.g., large social venues, industrial environments, or shopping malls.

Environment A: Medium size indoor environment

Photos of the medium size indoor environment are shown in Figure 3.31, visualizing the view from inside the room towards the array and from the array into the room. Due to the box shape of the room, the whole area of the room can be considered to be in LoS-condition, when no additional obstructions are introduced. Apart from that, the room is not empty, with shelves, tables, chairs and other lab equipment representing what can be termed a "cluttered" indoor environment. As a dedicated lab room, the room was locked during all measurements, resulting in a completely stationary environment inside the room over the course of measuring a synthetic LSA.

An advantage of this environment is that knowledge obtained from previous measurement campaigns in the medium size environment can be build on. While two walls are made from plaster-board and are known to spawn weaker reflections, the measurement area of the synthetic LSA is

Figure 3.30: Gain pattern of the designed wideband antenna including the absorber-plus-reflector construction. The subplots show the patterns at $f = \{3, 4, \dots, 10\}$ GHz covering the full frequency spectrum of interest. The gain patterns were measured in an antenna chamber with the antenna look direction pointing towards the ceiling (0 deg elevation).

located on an outside wall adjacent to the window side. Especially the windows¹ and the white-board on the door-side wall are expected to result in stronger reflections [25, 37]. A 3-dimensional model of the medium size environment was constructed is shown in Figure 3.32. It includes the measurement region (red shaded rectangle) representing the maximum area within which the mechanical positioner could move the antenna. Only a single synthetic LSA was measured in this environment. The UE devices are represented by a single antenna mounted on a tripod.

Three types of measurements are of interest in this environment:

- A small number of widely distributed points at different heights spread throughout the room. This setup is used to investigate variations in the visibility and amplitude effects for multipath components in LoS-condition.

¹The windows are metal coated, resulting in strong specular reflections.

(a) view towards measurement position

(b) view from measurement position

Figure 3.31: View from inside the room towards the array and from the array into the room. The measurement area that can be covered is indicated as red shaded rectangle. For ease of visualization the corners of the room are highlighted as red dotted lines.

- A trajectory of closely spaced points including increasing levels of obstruction. This setup can be used to investigate the effect of gradual obstruction and shadowing, e.g., the transition from LoS into NLoS, especially for the direct path and consistent effects observable over the measurement area.
- A closely spaced grid of measurement positions is recorded to obtain measurements containing scattering at the obstruction in form of the shelf.

Environment B: Large size indoor environment

The measurements performed in the large size environment are used to obtain insight into large open environments with strongly obstructed regions and changing visibility. Additionally, the much larger propagation distances show effects that can be expected in industrial settings such as large storage facilities or environments for large social gatherings such as concerts or sports venues.

In the large size environment both mechanical positioners are used for measurements, allowing to investigate a setup with distributed CSPs. Figure 3.33 shows photos of both mechanical positioners mounted in the environment with the measurement area highlighted as red and blue shaded rectangles for CSP₁ and CSP₂ respectively. Both synthetic CSPs are located at a height of $h = 2.85$ m (bottom edge of the measurement area) which represents the height in between ground floor and second floor, facing each other from a distance of $d \approx 25$ m apart. With the total height of the corridor up to the second floor of $h_{\text{corr.}} \approx 10.5 - 11.25$ m, the length of the corridor of $l_{\text{corr.}} \approx 76.5$ m and a width of $w_{\text{corr.}} \approx 3$ m, long delays in terms of multipath components are to be expected, in addition to obstruction in the seating areas on the ground floor in the middle between

Figure 3.32: Model of the medium size indoor environment. The measurement position at the wall is indicated as red shaded rectangle. The dimensions of the measurement area is 2.6 m × 1.5 m. Furniture is not included in the model, the whiteboard is outlined by a green dashed line, the windows are shown in blue.

(a) first measurement position, middle of the corridor

(b) second measurement position, end of the corridor

Figure 3.33: View from the ground floor the room towards both and from the array into the room. The maximum measurement area that can be covered is indicated as red and blue shaded areas, respectively. The height above ground floor level is $h = 2.85$ m at each location.

both measurement positions. The two CSPs are located in front of “bridges” connecting the offices on both sides of the building. Views of the measurement environment and a 3-dimensional model are shown in Figure 3.34. The environment model was generated based on laser scan measurements.

(a) view from corridor middle (CSP₁)

(b) view from corridor end (CSP₂)

(c) partial 3-dimensional model showing the region of interest in the large scale environment

Figure 3.34: Large size indoor environment photos and 3-dimensional model constructed from laser scan measurements of the environment. The photos in Figure 3.34a and Figure 3.34b include the opposite measurement position in the respective color corresponding to the 3D model in 3.34c and Figure 3.33.

In this scenario the dipole antennas were used at the mobile device. While this is not optimal in the large scale environment, these antennas were nonetheless chosen as the omnidirectional pattern in the horizontal plane would result in similar antenna characteristics towards both of the locations of the mechanical positioners. The UE devices are again represented by a single antenna mounted on a tripod. A photo of measurement region as observed from the measurement position at the end of the corridor (position in blue) can be seen in Figure 3.35.

In this environment three types of measurements are of interest:

- Distributed points at different heights were measured in between the shelves and in the corner (in NLoS) and one position in the corridor (in LoS). This setup is used to investigate variations in the visibility and amplitude effects for multipath components.
- A trajectory of closely spaced points transitioning between LoS and NLoS.
- Closely spaced positions in close proximity to the shelves to measure scattering effects.

(a) from CSP₂

(b) from ground floor

Figure 3.35: Measurement region in the large scale indoor environment model as seen from the corridor end towards the corridor middle (red). To obtain more a realistic scenario additional obstructions from metal shelves filled with water bottles were set up.

3.3.3 Description of UE Setups

The performed measurements target different applications in terms of UE setups as well as use-cases that are of interest for RW. The investigated setups can be separated into three groups (1-3) consisting of UE positions covering a larger spatial area or closely spaced positions to analyze local variations, the case of an obstruction or no obstruction being present, or trajectory measurements targeting the spatial consistency of moving UEs (or local-to-global propagation conditions). In summary the types of measurements are as follows:

- 1 wide distribution of measurement points (i.e., UEs)
- 2 closely spaced measurements points (i.e., UEs)
- 3 trajectory through environment (i.e., a moving UE)
 - a scenario without obstruction (i.e., clear LoS condition)
 - b scenario with obstruction (i.e., signal blockage due to objects)

The different measurements that were performed are summarized below, including parameters of the measurement devices.

- “***distributed***”: Distributed positions in medium and large scale environment – if main interest for channel modeling to analyze propagation characteristics at specific locations in the environment, positions X1-2, M1-6 shown in Figure 3.36a and L1-5, L8 showing in Figure 3.36c.
- “***trajectory medium***”: Trajectories in medium scale environment – single CSP on a wall, performed in medium scale environment, passing from LoS into NLoS, of interest for (use cases 2, 4, 5, 10, 11 from [11]). Metal shelves (e.g., supermarket scenario) are used as obstruction to generate a realistic scenario, trajectory T1 in Figure 3.36b.
- “***on-shelf***”: Mobile device directly before shelf – a region around/before a shelf filled with water bottles is scanned at regular grid points, e.g., spaced at $\lambda/4$, these will be used for

Table 3.5: Measurement configurations used for different scenarios.

	“distributed”	“on-shelf”	“trajectory medium”	“trajectory large”
environment	medium (A)	medium (A)/large (B)	medium (A)	large (B)
device	CS/VNA/VNA	VNA	VNA	VNA
P1 (RX1, portal 1)	slot	slot	slot	slot
P2 (RX2, portal 2)			slot	slot
P3 (TX1)	slot	slot	dipole	dipole
max. distance	176/200/400 m	200 m	200 m	200 m
freq. spacing	-/1600/750 kHz	1600 kHz	1600 kHz	1600 kHz
freq. range	3-10/3-9/3-9 GHz	3-9 GHz	3-9 GHz	3-9 GHz
time/freq. samples	1067/8001/4001	4001	4001	4001
measurement group	1ab	2b	3ab	3ab

validation of WPT algorithms and to analyzing focusing capabilities in algorithm development (positions L6, L7 in Figure 3.36c).

- “**trajectory large**”: Trajectory in large scale environment – two CSPs on opposite ends of a corridor, passing from LoS into NLoS, of interest for (use cases 2, 4, 5, 10, 11 from [11]). Metal shelves (e.g., supermarket scenario) are used as obstruction to generate a realistic scenario (trajectory C1 in Figure 3.36c).
- “**user dummy**”: Human dummy related – these will cover all the VR and augmented reality use cases (use cases 1, 7, 12 from [11]), previously UWB measurements were performed in a single-input single-output (SISO) setup giving valuable insight, for these types of measurements a human head dummy was 3D printed to be used in further application specific measurements and for algorithms development.

The settings as well as antenna configurations for the different measurement campaigns are summarized in Table 3.5.

Figure 3.36: Visualization of measurement locations in medium and large size environments. (a) points distributed in medium size environment, (b) trajectory including obstruction in medium size environment, (c) distributed points and trajectory in large size environment.

Figure 3.37: Setup used in the visualization of signal propagation. Measurements were performed at two positions X1 and X2 to get initial insight into expected propagation and measurement system capabilities.

3.3.4 Measurement Results and Analysis

For any type of array based system, simplified propagation models are usually applied that are, obviously, accurate enough when the corresponding conditions are fulfilled. Probably the most famous assumption in array processing is the plane wave assumption [21, 24, 43] where the phase shift or delay at each array element is approximated by a linear model that is independent of the distance. Additionally, each MPC amplitudes is approximated to be constant for the whole array, neglecting propagation loss along the array aperture as well as differences due to the array element patterns. With increasing size of the employed arrays, these effects will no longer be valid and introduce errors due to model mismatch. These effects are essential to practically all fields of application of the RW system. The UWB measurement campaign thus targets the effects of MPC visibility and amplitude effects that are characteristic for arrays with a large aperture [4, 12, 28]. Note that as we investigate deterministic propagation effects in terms of specular MPCs only a subset of all measurements will be presented here to highlight both positive and negative aspects that are important to consider.

Non-parametric Analysis

Especially for UWB signals, the time-domain signals contain valuable information, while allowing an intuitive interpretation without the need for algorithms. This section presents a non-parametric approach to the measurement analysis, showing time-domain signals for different array elements, comparing single snapshots over all array elements and in form of spherical beamformer spectra relying solely on the array geometry.

Time-domain signal visualization: Based on the measurements performed with the channel sounder, useful insights into the system capabilities in terms of system resolution, propagation effects, but also measurement can be obtained. As stated above, the channel sounder allows to directly measure the time-domain channel responses over a frequency band of 3.8 – 10.2 GHz while keeping full phase coherency between measurements. For the visualization purpose, the bandwidth was reduced to $BW = 3.5$ GHz by filtering with a raised cosine filter with roll-off factor of $\beta_{RC} = 0.6$ during post processing. The LSA used here contains $M = 3200$ antenna elements spaced at $\lambda/2 \approx 2.16$ cm for the carrier frequency $f_c = 6.95$ GHz, representing a $(N_x \times N_z) = (80 \times 40)$ uniform rectangular array (URA) of physical dimensions of roughly $(1.7 \text{ m} \times 0.84 \text{ m})$. The LSA was located on the wall in the medium size environment, see Figure 3.37.

A subset of the measured signals is shown in Figure 3.38 for two agent positions X1 and X2, with

Figure 3.38: Received signals for the URA from Figure 3.37 of size $(N_x \times N_z) = (80 \times 40)$. Signals are shown for bottom ($m_z = 1$) and top row ($m_z = 40$) of array elements.

the y-axis showing the propagation delay in m and the x-axis the index of the array element for each row, with the first array element being the ones located closest to the windows. The signals are shown for all $N_x = 80$ array elements of the bottom row (Figure 3.38a and 3.38c, closest to the floor) and top row (Figure 3.38b and 3.38d, closest to the ceiling) of the array. Note that each position is normalized separately with darker colors representing higher signal amplitude. For both positions (and rows), the LoS component clearly shows the wavefront curvature due to the size of the array. The amplitude variations and varying visibility of MPCs at different array elements are well visible, e.g., MPCs are gradually attenuated or abruptly appear and/or disappear). These effects are visible both when comparing the signals of the rows of one position, but also when comparing the signals of different array elements of the same row. A good example for position X1 is the component that abruptly appears at col. index 20 with a delay of approx. 14.5 m (marked as light blue circle) for the top row (i.e., $m_z = 40$, Figure 3.38b), but is never visible for the bottom for of array elements (i.e., $m_z = 1$, Figure 3.38a). At this large system bandwidth it becomes clear that full use of the array data will require parametric algorithms that can deal with this varying component visibility, i.e., taking the signal model outlined above into account.

Regarding spherical wave propagation, the wavefront curvature is clearly visible, especially for the direct path where the UE is in the array near field, but reduces in prominence for increasing delays, i.e., when moving into the array far field. In addition to this curvature that introduces distance related amplitude "variations" over time, the additional path loss likewise affects the received signal power due to the large measurement area, i.e., when the transmitting/receiving device is in the array near field where the distinct propagation distances towards each array element results in noticeably different attenuation [21].

While these effects are visually observable at the ultrawide measurement bandwidth, they will also take effect in the expected bandwidth region of RW, i.e., for the signal phase or the underlying amplitudes of overlapping MPCs.

Spatial-domain signal visualization: Viewing the measured channel responses in the spatial domain for specific "snapshots" (propagation delays) shows how MPCs propagate along the mea-

Figure 3.39: Snapshots of time-domain signals obtained using the VNA for specific time instances for different measurement locations (M1, M4). The signals are shown per array element covering the full measurement area (see Figure 3.36a) using the full measurement bandwidth of 7 GHz.

surement area. While this is best achieved by generating videos of the propagating signal, we include specific snapshots of exemplary measurement positions (M1 and M4, see Figure 3.36a) that highlight conditions that the RW needs to be able to cover. Furthermore, these snapshots will prove helpful in the following sections where a parametric channel estimator is used to analyze component visibility and amplitude distributions.

Figure 3.39 show 4 snapshots for measurement positions M1 and M4 (see Figure 3.36a). With position M1 being directly in front of the measurement area, the propagating spherical wave is seen clearly in panel Figure 3.39a-(1), with the wave impinging briefly before and arriving at the border of the measurement area in Figure 3.39a-(2) after the corresponding duration. The effect of propagation attenuation concurring with the non-ideal antenna gain patterns (most likely resulting in additional attenuation) is clearly observable. Specular multipath components can be seen in Figure 3.39a-(3-4), which also show the amplitude variations, visibility regions, as well as dispersion due to reflection in the environment. The same effects are observable for the snapshots of position M4 shown in Figure 3.39b, with the snapshots Figure 3.39b-(3-4) again highlighting that the component visibility changes along the full array. Especially for M4, comparing the noise level before arrival of the direct path (hor. indices below 50 in Figure 3.39b-(1)) with later snapshots shows that in addition to strong specular MPCs also a significant portion of signal energy will be contained in diffuse reflections that produce strong(er) fading patterns.

Spherical beamformer spectra: An easy way to analyze array data is by performing beamforming [24] (extended to account for spherical wave propagation using the defined channel vectors/matrices from (2.3) or (2.5) as beamforming weights for location-based beamforming) which can be seen as a simple but effective non-parametric channel estimator. Even when neglecting the visibility effects highlighted in the previous sections, using a standard beamformer and considering spherical wave propagation on the measurement data shows an informative snapshot of

Figure 3.40: Spherical wave beamformer spectra for position M1 in the medium size environment using the full data (full bandwidth, all array elements). The azimuth-elevation power spectrum shown in Figure 3.40b represents the view as seen from the measurement region shown in Figure 3.31. 0 deg azimuth points towards the windows, 0 deg elevation towards the ceiling.

the environment as perceived using the full array.

Figure 3.40 shows the obtained full 3-dimensional beamformer spectrum for position M1 in terms of 2-dimensional projections onto all combinations of delay, azimuth and elevation. The azimuth-elevation power spectrum shown in Figure 3.40b represents the view as seen from the measurement region shown in Figure 3.31, with the azimuth angle of 0 deg pointing towards the windows and the elevation angle of 0 deg towards the ceiling.

Starting with the azimuth-elevation spectrum (Figure 3.40b) a number of specular MPCs is observable in addition to what could be termed diffuse components. The same effects are observable in the remaining spectra for azimuth-delay and elevation-delay, showing similar combinations of specular and diffuse MPCs. By jointly using all of these spectra, it is possible to find locations of origin of specular MPCs which would in turn allow to build an image source model to represent the deterministic propagation part contained in the channel model describe in Ch. 2. While this beamforming approach shows specular MPCs impinging on the array and theoretically allows to exploit the full spatial resolution, the visibility information of MPCs is lost. In later sections, a parametric channel estimator will be used on subarrays (of the full array) which allows to analyze MPC visibility due to the better resolution that can generally be obtained with a parametric estimator (at the cost of introducing artifacts due to possible model mismatch). The use of the full measurement aperture and bandwidth also highlights a trade-off effect that will be important in algorithms developed for RW:

- a large aperture allows to form narrow beams
- a large bandwidths yields a high delay resolution

When reducing the system bandwidth, keeping the spatial resolution high will be of prime interest. Assuming that the RW system consists of small-aperture CSPs, these will need to be fused efficiently to obtain the large aperture of the full system.

Figure 3.41: Signal power computed by performing position-based beamforming for direct path, window and whiteboard reflection at the example of position M1 using the environment model.

Geometry-based Analysis

After the non-parametric analysis, we now exploit the environment model to investigate diffraction and shadowing effects in the environment and visibility and amplitude effects of specific MPCs. Note that while this model based analysis gives valuable insights, improved models still need to be obtained by dedicated algorithms allowing to learn the environment representation on the corresponding level that is suitable for specific applications. In this case, the focus lies on the environment geometry and spatial propagation characteristics.

Power distribution of modeled components: To analyze the power of MPCs derived from an environment model we use an image source model as introduced in Section 2.2. Each reflection surface is represented by an equivalent virtual source that represents an MPC in terms of AOA, AOD, time-of-arrival (TOA) as well as amplitudes. As all of these parameters depend on the actual environment and are usually not known exactly, we compute the image sources corresponding to a specific environment surface and then average the power over a small grid around the modeled source location. All computations are performed per-array element, to allow analysis of spatially local effects.

Results are shown in Figure 3.41 for three components: the direct path, the window reflection and the whiteboard reflection. The direct path amplitudes (see Figure 3.41a) show the expected attenuation due to the propagation distance dependent path loss differences on the one hand, as well as due to the non-uniform gain pattern of the antenna. As patch antennas were used at both the LSA as well as at the UE, the gain pattern affect arises twice (at both ends of the link). Apart from that, the full LSA is in LoS condition with respect to the direct path. The window reflection in turn (see Figure 3.41b) shows much stronger amplitude variations, as well as a limited region where the signal power is within 10 dB of the maximum over the array area. The shape of the area of higher power shows a good correspondence with features from the environment. As can be observed in Figure 3.31 the cupboard (outlined in green) located besides the area of the LSA acts as an obstruction to on the one hand partially shield the window reflection and on the other hand introduce fading patterns. Lastly, at the example of the whiteboard (see Figure 3.41c) a similar effect of partial visibility can be observed.

Similar effects can be seen by in depth investigation of further model components, which will not be included here for the sake of conciseness. Additionally, with increasing order of reflections

this type of analysis will become prone to increasing model mismatch as small measurement inaccuracies accumulate. Still, these results show the validity and importance of including visibility regions for environment geometry-related MPCs.

Diffraction and shadowing at edges: In Section 2.2, we introduce a geometry-based channel model which models the visibility of MPCs. This ray-tracing based approach attempts to model whether the path between a transmit antenna and receive antenna is obstructed by some object. However, at the sub-10 GHz frequencies RW is operating at, diffraction is a propagation phenomenon that significantly impacts the transmission of radio signals. We take the measurements of the trajectory indicated in Figure 3.36 and analyze the first 20 positions spaced at $\Delta_y = 3$ cm. We divide the transmitting CSP₁ into *columns*, i.e., into ULA-subarrays parallel to the z -axis, and transmit radio signals to the antenna moving along the trajectory.

We perform position-based MRT from all antennas within a column-ULA to a single position along the trajectory at a time. That is, we construct modeled channel vectors $\mathbf{h}_{\text{model}}$ (see [2] for more details) based only on the individual distances between all involved antennas. We compute the individual beamforming weights

$$\mathbf{w} = \frac{\mathbf{h}^*}{\|\mathbf{h}\|} \quad (3.5)$$

and with these the path gain

$$PG = |\mathbf{w}^\top \mathbf{h}|^2 \quad (3.6)$$

showing the received power for a specific position along the trajectory. For the computation of the precoding weights \mathbf{w} , i.e., the geometry-based beamforming weights, we ignore the environment and thus use LoS-beams only. From Figure 3.36, it is clearly visible that some positions along the trajectory are shadowed by a wall. Despite the shadowing of the direct path, diffraction would in theory allow the waves to bend around the edge to some extent.

The results of our analysis are depicted in Figure 3.42. The horizontal axis of the plots shows the angle between the x -axis and the vectorial distance between the edge (boundary between free-space and wall) and the trajectory position. The vertical axis only shows the indices of the column-ULAs. According to a ray-tracing model with visibility regions, there would be no power received at positions right of the dashed black line (indicating where a column of the array would not be visible at a certain position along the trajectory). However, diffraction may enable to still receive usable amounts of power behind the corner. The analysis has been conducted for the frequencies $f = \{3, 4, 5\}$ GHz. As expected, with higher frequencies, and thus smaller wavelengths, the effect seems to decrease. Along the vertical axis in Figure 3.42, there is a strong fading pattern visible which is likely to originate from constructive and destructive interference with MPCs from the walls which are in *parallel* to the uniform linear arrays (ULAs). Thus, the fading cannot be improved through antenna diversity in that geometric dimension. However, the figures show clearly, that the use of multiple ULAs (columns) will provide a good (stable) power budget before the edge.

Super-resolution channel estimation: To analyze the radio channels in different environments we proceed by employing a super-resolution channel estimation algorithm in form of a sparse Bayesian learning (SBL)-based algorithm based on the algorithm proposed in [17]. This allows the decomposition of the radio channel into MPCs based on a signal model of the form of (2.1).

Figure 3.42: Diffraction at an edge for frequencies $f = \{3, 4, 5\}$ GHz. Geometry-based (column-wise) MRT to the first 20 positions of the trajectory C1 from in Figure 3.36 is employed using synthetic CSP_1 . Positions right of the dashed black line are shadowed according to the floor plan, with φ denoting the angle between the x -axis and the vectorial distance from the corner to the trajectory positions. (The plots have been interpolated for better visualization.)

While obtaining an accurate decomposition requires the model to be correct, i.e., perfect calibration of the antennas in form of known direction-response, a lot of insight can still be obtained when keeping the inevitable model mismatch in mind in the analysis. The SBL-algorithm provides as results, the estimated amplitudes, delays and AOA's of MPCs. To investigate the visibility of specific environment features, data association (DA) needs to be performed. This stage uses the obtained MPC estimates and find the optimum association to a fixed number of *modeled* components, which were chosen manually after visual inspection of the measurement data.

With application to the full array jointly not being feasible due to the large number of signal samples and array elements in combination with the (slightly) more complex model of spherical wave propagation resulting in a drastic increase in computation time, we apply the SBL only to subarrays of size (4×4) or (8×8) . While the larger subarray with $M = 64$ array elements will provide a good resolution when combined with a bandwidth in the UWB regime, the small 16-element subarrays are of interest as they allow flexible processing with corresponding hardware already commercially available, and intended to be used as the basic building block in the testbed being developed in WP5.

We start this section by presenting the channel estimation results obtained with the SBL-algorithm, which is the basis for the following evaluation of MPC visibility, an analysis of the feasibility of the MPC-based model in general and obstruction effects in dynamic scenarios.

Channel estimation results: The results obtained by applying a super resolution channel estimation algorithm to the measurement data are discussed in this section. Figure 3.43 shows the results for two subarrays of dimension (4×4) evaluated for measurement position M1 (see Figure 3.36). The figures show the angular power spectrum of the signal before application of the channel estimation, the residual angular power spectrum after subtracting the number of compo-

Figure 3.43: SBL performance showing estimated components over the angle-spectrum, residual angle-spectrum and residual time-domain signals. Results are shown for 4×4 subarrays with 500 MHz bandwidth.

ponents that were found as well as the time-domain signals for all 16 array elements. The subarrays that were used are $s = \{14, 500\}$ out of a total number of $N_s = 504$, with the lower indexed subarray being in the first column of subarrays closest to the window and the higher indexed subarray being in the last column of subarrays, closest to the door side wall. To allow easier inspection of the results for the spectra, the angular spectra *before* subtracting the estimates were normalized to unit power.

The angular spectra before removing any estimated components shown in Figure 3.43a and 3.43d shows the expected low resolution of a standard beamformer. While the maximum corresponds to the direct path direction (at least in this case of LoS condition), components apart from that cannot be resolved properly. This can in turn be achieved by a super-resolution channel estimation algorithm, here obtained by applying an SBL algorithm to the data of the (4×4) array with a bandwidth of 500 MHz and an inter-element spacing corresponding to $\Delta = \lambda/2$ of the carrier frequency of $f_c = 6$ GHz. Estimated components are shown as circles with size corresponding to the estimated component amplitude. The color in turn indicates whether the estimate could be associated to one of the $K_{\text{model}} = 8$ modeled components (red +) or not (cyan or magenta respectively). The numbering of the components carries over to the time-domain plots in Figure 3.43c and 3.43f. While more components are estimated than modeled for both of

the shown subarrays, which is not unexpected and always the case, the associated components show a sufficiently accurate correspondence. After subtracting all estimated components, the residual signal is again evaluated in terms of the angular-spectrum, see Figure 3.43b and 3.43e. This shows that much of the signal power is covered by the estimates, while still leaving residual power, albeit much less than contained in the estimates. The same effect can be seen in the plots of the time-domain signals (black) and residuals alongside (blue) the estimates (green for signal and cyan/red circles for estimated parameters) and modeled components (red dashed and circled numbers) in Figure 3.43c and 3.43f (the estimated noise level is shown as solid red line). The strongest components are removed, while some signal power is still left in the residual, which is due to the fact that the channel estimation was stopped after finding a fixed number of $K = 20$ components. While this stopping condition does not allowing the algorithm to fully converge, it speeds up the estimation procedure and is reasonable as the remaining low-power components would have little effect on the already found (stronger) estimates.

An overview of the SBL-estimates obtained for measurement positions M1-M6 are given in Tab. 3.6. The table compares the estimated components energy (as percentage of the full signal energy) sorted from strongest to weakest for the 6 strongest components, the SNR in similar sorting form and the energy percentage of the components associated to the 8 modeled components. The results are shown in terms of mean and standard deviation taken over all $N_s = 500$ subarrays. To compare how well the channel estimator can represent the total signal energy, the total estimated energy is compared with the residual energy and, for the SNR case, the signal SNR. Comparing the results for the different measurement positions shows that a high percentage of the signal energy is covered by all estimated components, with usually close to 95% energy contained in the 20 estimated components. The significantly lower percentage of 82% for M4 can be explained by the close proximity to metal shelves, from which a larger number of scattered components can be expected which would result in a large number of components containing lower power. This possible explanation is supported by the SNR comparison, where the residual SNR is basically identical for all positions, with the SNR of the estimates closely resembling the signal SNR.

Note that the SNR values would be affected by increasing the number of components to estimate before stopping the SBL as this will affect the estimated noise level. Nonetheless, these results support the validity of the channel model for RW that includes both deterministic MPCs as well as stochastic (e.g., scattered or diffusely reflected) components.

Table 3.6: Table summarizing the energy of estimated components in dB and as percentage of the total received signal energy. The first rows compare the ordered list of components, starting from strongest to second strongest and so on. The last part shows the energy percentage of components associated to environment features indicated as direct path, *win.-wall* (2nd order reflection over windows and door-side wall), and so on.

(4 × 4), 500 MHz	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6
component	component energy in % of received signal energy (as mean ± std.dev.)					
strongest	85.86 ± 6.50	76.56 ± 15.39	67.28 ± 9.40	43.32 ± 14.65	85.41 ± 17.52	65.28 ± 9.10
2nd strongest	3.95 ± 1.99	4.76 ± 4.67	9.73 ± 5.48	16.12 ± 8.27	6.75 ± 9.53	14.98 ± 8.12
3rd	2.18 ± 1.35	1.42 ± 1.37	3.95 ± 2.36	6.77 ± 4.17	1.22 ± 1.56	6.12 ± 3.64
4th	1.19 ± 0.64	0.79 ± 0.71	2.43 ± 1.07	4.26 ± 1.95	0.69 ± 0.64	2.88 ± 1.56
5th	0.80 ± 0.38	0.54 ± 0.45	1.82 ± 0.74	3.17 ± 1.35	0.46 ± 0.43	1.84 ± 0.82
6th	0.62 ± 0.30	0.40 ± 0.34	1.38 ± 0.55	2.46 ± 0.98	0.35 ± 0.32	1.30 ± 0.46
∑ over 20	96.51 ± 1.17	97.89 ± 1.61	91.19 ± 2.87	82.36 ± 4.70	97.84 ± 1.76	94.11 ± 1.61
residual	3.16 ± 1.06	1.91 ± 1.46	7.98 ± 2.60	15.98 ± 4.25	1.95 ± 1.59	5.33 ± 1.45
	SNR in dB (as mean ± std.dev.)					
strongest	26.35 ± 1.58	28.89 ± 3.60	21.26 ± 1.84	16.06 ± 2.37	29.70 ± 4.31	22.80 ± 1.55
2nd strongest	12.51 ± 2.78	14.89 ± 3.74	12.17 ± 2.92	11.32 ± 3.00	16.09 ± 5.21	15.82 ± 2.25
3rd	9.73 ± 2.83	10.30 ± 2.48	8.38 ± 2.14	7.61 ± 2.30	9.40 ± 2.81	11.87 ± 2.69
4th	7.23 ± 2.20	7.58 ± 2.42	6.50 ± 1.71	5.82 ± 1.92	7.20 ± 2.42	8.77 ± 2.28
5th	5.60 ± 1.83	5.87 ± 2.08	5.28 ± 1.60	4.59 ± 1.73	5.54 ± 1.89	6.99 ± 1.89
6th	4.46 ± 1.69	4.63 ± 1.78	4.12 ± 1.54	3.53 ± 1.66	4.39 ± 1.60	5.58 ± 1.56
∑ over 20	26.87 ± 1.37	30.06 ± 3.21	22.62 ± 1.56	19.09 ± 1.43	30.39 ± 3.97	24.43 ± 1.21
residual	11.81 ± 0.00	11.81 ± 0.00	11.81 ± 0.00	11.82 ± 0.00	11.81 ± 0.00	11.81 ± 0.00
signal	27.02 ± 1.32	30.15 ± 3.14	23.03 ± 1.42	19.94 ± 1.18	30.48 ± 3.90	24.70 ± 1.13
	component energy in % of received signal energy (as mean ± std.dev.)					
direct path (1)	85.86 ± 6.50	76.28 ± 16.26	66.87 ± 10.67	36.61 ± 17.72	38.66 ± 41.41	61.01 ± 19.31
window (2)	1.94 ± 1.71	0.41 ± 0.68	2.91 ± 3.38	2.03 ± 2.38	0.32 ± 0.54	6.76 ± 5.06
window-doorwall (3)	0.63 ± 0.60	0.54 ± 1.10	0.56 ± 0.30	1.20 ± 0.80	0.36 ± 0.55	1.19 ± 0.83
window-whiteboard (4)	0.31 ± 0.23	0.08 ± 0.04	0.60 ± 0.30	0.59 ± 0.11		0.26 ± 0.14
whiteboard (5)	0.51 ± 0.47	0.22 ± 0.19	1.48 ± 0.96	3.99 ± 2.84	0.14 ± 0.12	0.37 ± 0.18
floor (6)	1.04 ± 1.01	0.81 ± 0.92	1.83 ± 1.12	0.92 ± 0.77	0.13 ± 0.18	1.79 ± 1.66
ceiling (7)	0.23 ± 0.15	0.07 ± 0.07	2.29 ± 2.24	0.63 ± 0.25	0.10 ± 0.08	0.59 ± 0.42
doorwall (8)	2.52 ± 2.15	1.18 ± 1.85	8.23 ± 6.13	11.98 ± 13.99	0.94 ± 2.48	9.50 ± 9.13
∑ over 8	91.00 ± 6.29	77.81 ± 16.82	81.21 ± 6.72	23.92 ± 10.27	84.38 ± 18.73	82.15 ± 6.02

Component amplitude distribution: In this section we investigate the visibility and spatial amplitude distribution of the obtained channel estimates, comparing results obtained for different subarray dimensions ($M = \{16, 64\}$) in terms of performance for measurement positions M1-M6 (see Figure 3.36a). The spatial amplitude distributions of the SBL-estimates for selected environment features in terms of the associated components amplitudes are shown in Figure 3.44 alongside the computed geometric visibility obtained via ray tracing using the environment model and the known measurement positions.

Starting from the direct path, which is visible along the full array, both small and large subarray dimensions results in a similar distribution of amplitudes. The combined effect of the antenna gain pattern is again observable, with the amplitudes compensated for distance dependent path loss. For the window reflection, the obtained strongly resemble the results obtained in the geometry-based non-parametric analysis: even though geometric visibility would be given as the cupboard (see Figure 3.31) was not included in the environment model, only the upper half of subarrays obtain sufficiently large amplitude estimates for a reflection associated to the window.

This type of partial visibility can be better visualized in the last two rows of plots, showing the results for the (first order) whiteboard reflection and for the (second order) window-door/door wall reflection. The whiteboard reflection is only visible in a rectangular shape over an upper right region of the full array (see Figure 3.44g), which represents the subarray regions where components were found that could be associated to the corresponding image source. Note that differences between the smaller and larger subarray size can be attributed to the increased array gain of the larger array, where low SNR components are “easier” detected. Similarly, the second order reflection in the bottom row is only visible for subarrays above row number 4 (vertically) shown in Figure 3.44j, with the amplitudes of associated estimates above a certain level again arising a region of similar shape, i.e., almost all associated estimates stem from subarrays above vertical row 5.

The measurements in the large size environment, i.e., in the corridor, show similar effects, with a better observability of the effect of the limited extent of the reflecting surface(s). At the example of measurement position L1 using CSP₂, results are shown in Figure 3.45 for 4×4 subarrays with a bandwidth of 500 MHz. The figures again show the computed visibility (top row of subplots) and the amplitude estimates obtained with the SBL algorithm (bottom row) for selected (first order reflection) components alongside the direct path. Starting with the direct path (Figure 3.45a and 3.45d) the general LoS condition of the channel is clearly visible. Nonetheless, strong variations in the estimated amplitude occur which is very likely due to overlap between the side wall reflections (see Figure 3.34b). For the reflection via the right wall (Figure 3.45b and 3.45e) the visibility computed from the environment model shows a triangular region of component invisibility in the bottom right corner of the CSP, which corresponds to the region of large estimated amplitudes. Note that this specific geometric shape is due to the seating area underneath the right wall (see again Figure 3.34b) with the wall edge representing the boundary between the *visible* (blue) and *not visible* (yellow) regions. The left wall in turn shows again stronger variations regarding the amplitudes and a less clear correspondence with the model visibility. Again, these variations can be attributed to the geometric configuration of the measurement setup: as the measurement location is rather close to the corresponding image source, path overlap in the delay as well as angle domain is again a likely cause for the observable variations.

Similar effects are observable at the rest of the measurement locations, with the obstruction by the shelves clearly visibly. Regarding algorithm development, these measurements are very important as they highlight the necessity to be able to deal with complex reflection environments, where

Figure 3.44: Estimated amplitudes obtained with the SBL-algorithm from [17]. Subarrays of size (4 × 4) and (8 × 8) are used, both with 500 MHz bandwidth for direct path and selected first order reflections.

Figure 3.45: Estimated amplitudes obtained with the SBL-algorithm from [17]. Subarrays of size (4×4) are used with 500 MHz bandwidth, comparing two first order reflections.

the limited component visibility and consequently varying number of components and received signal power needs to be considered in parametric approaches as well as in non parametric approaches.

Consistency of shadowing during motion: After analysing the visibility of environment components, we investigate the effects of obstruction in a similar fashion. In this case, we focus on effects on the direct path, as this usually the path that can be used to transfer most of the power towards the UE and is thus strongest affected by obstructions. The scenario that is used for the analysis are the trajectory positions T1-T43 recorded in the medium size environment (see Figure 3.36b). The SBL is again applied to subarrays of dimension (4×4) using a bandwidth of 1 GHz, with the obtained estimates again associated to the same model components as before. As obstruction, two metal shelves that were filled with two layers of wideband absorbers and binders filled with paper were used, which resulted in almost complete obstruction when the UE is located in full NLoS condition, i.e., with the shelves in between LSA and UE.

The results are shown in Figure 3.46 for trajectory positions T1, T15 and T30, again as amplitude distributions over all subarrays. With the starting position T1 of the trajectory being at a similar location as M1, the effect of the obstruction is visible for subarrays farthest from the window which are already obstructed (hor. index 18), while the subarrays closest to the window (hor. index 1) do not experience obstruction. When moving along the trajectory, the shadowed area is continuously increased as clearly visible in Figure 3.46b and 3.46c. The observed effect is similar to what was reported in the wideband measurements presented in Section 3.2.

3.4 Summarized Propagation Characteristics

This section gives a summary of the key propagation characteristics that were identified in the measurement campaigns.

From the dynamic RW measurements, the main conclusion is that the channel is spatially non-

Figure 3.46: Estimated amplitudes obtained with the SBL-algorithm from [17]. Subarrays of size (4×4) for 1 GHz bandwidth. The direct path amplitudes are analyzed along the trajectory to show the spatial effect of the obstruction.

stationary, the different links see different channels. The Gamma distribution best captures the overall statistics of the small-scale fading. In the sensing scenario, when all radios are static, all variations in the channel are due to moving objects blocking MPCs or creating additional scattering components that interact with the MPCs of the static channel. For the limited bandwidth a single exponential will suffice to model the delay spread.

From the wideband synthetic array measurements, we conclude that both the deterministic and stochastic parts of the channel show non-wide sense stationary properties for RW. Especially, the fading statistics of SSF and LSF may vary over subarrays or different propagation conditions. These varying channel characteristics should be considered for RW channel modeling with . Non-wide sense stationary properties can potentially be exploited to reduce the computational complexity by processing only the most relevant CSPs, e.g., measurements from power-concentrated subarrays.

From the dynamic measurements it is clear that the distributed CSPs complement each other and provide extreme diversity. It should however be noted that there can be significant power variations due to large differences between antenna elements, and a few effective links might dominate. From a sensing perspective the advantages of the multiple coherent receivers are clear from the measurements, both when it comes to locating an active UEs or locating a passive but moving user. The many link combinations within the RW offer a good diversity to separate objects from each other.

From the UWB measurements, the main aspects that will be important in the modeling approach are threefold, namely the importance of multipath propagation, the geometry related visibility of said multipath components, and the necessity to employ correct models to describe propagation in the array near field. First, multipath propagation can be linked to and described by a geometric environment model which allows to capture a large portion of the propagating signal energy. This was shown in the static measurements and analyzed in terms of the energy portion that is described by estimated multipath components and multipath components associated to features in a geometric environment model including image sources. Second, the resulting variations in component visibility will be important in location aware applications, where the measured channel is used to estimate the used location or infer environment parameters. Both of these are expected to be heavily coupled with the number of visible MPCs. Third, the propagation along RW is no longer expected to fulfill narrowband as well as certain wideband assumptions, with spherical waves propagating along the full RW. The plane wave assumption will only be valid for a small

region of the RW, allowing to use efficient algorithms can be employed for channel estimation.

In summary, both the wideband and ultrawideband measurement campaigns have shown the need to take the spatial non stationarity into account. Especially with the envisioned large RW aperture this has to be accounted for.

Chapter 4

Models for RadioWeaves

This chapter discusses the further insights regarding the channel model that can be derived from the measurements and the corresponding analysis. Regarding specific fields of application in the RW system, we show that the model is flexible and able to deal with all requirements. It is furthermore easy to adapt and allows to perform further refinements should these be deemed necessary in future workpackages.

4.1 Considerations Regarding the Channel Model

The analysis of the performed measurements supports the described channel model and allows to further specify aspects that enable efficient use in algorithms or simply as simulation environment to quantify performance. For the deterministic part containing MPCs and describing their relation to a specific environment geometry, the visibility of MPC is introduced to the model.

4.1.1 Deterministic Model

Components containing position-related information relate to the environment geometry via a suitable model, e.g., an image source model, as described Chapter 2. As discussed in the measurement analysis, the visibility effects regarding specific environment features will result in the number of MPCs in (2.2) to vary depending on the location of CSPs as well as UEs. As outlined before, classical array processing, where the size of the antenna array is small compared to the propagation distance and system bandwidth, allows to use simplifying assumptions such as plane wave propagation and negligible propagation attenuation along the array [15, 21]. In the context of LSAs that were investigated in the measurements, these assumptions are not fulfilled for the full array. It is in turn necessary to take propagation characteristics along the array into account as already described in the channel model, or to separate the full array into subarrays where the classical assumptions are valid [21]. To fuse the information from subarrays it is then again necessary to accurately consider the propagation characteristics along the full array. The amplitude model allows to take this propagation along the array into account, by defining the MPC amplitudes as

$$\tilde{\alpha}_{k,m}^{(j)} \propto \frac{\tilde{\alpha}_{k,m}^{(j)} b(\varphi_{k,m}^{(j)}, \theta_{k,m}^{(j)})}{c\tau_{k,m}^{(j)}} f_{k,m}^{(j)} \quad (4.1)$$

where $b(\cdot)$ is the complex-valued antenna gain pattern depending on the azimuth and elevation of the correspondent MPC at the m th array element. The quantity $\tilde{\alpha}_{k,m}^{(j)}$ on the right hand side of (4.1) would then become an “effective” MPC amplitude and represents the environment-related, path loss compensated MPC amplitude, i.e., the amplitude related to transmit power and attenuation due to reflection at different materials. Note that for a specific MPC k , the effective amplitude $\tilde{\alpha}_{k,m}^{(j)}$ can vary per array element when reflection properties of materials depend on the angle of incidence of the MPCs. The visibility is considered by the factor $f_{k,m}^{(j)}$, which is $f_{k,m}^{(j)} = 1$ if the component k is visible at array element m of anchor j and $f_{k,m}^{(j)} = 0$ otherwise. Especially the MPC visibility can be modeled efficiently by simply considering polygon shaped regions which will be especially helpful for algorithms that rely on efficiently dealing with effects related to component visibility. When not used in algorithms directly, the visibility can be used to select subarrays where the channels are stationary, e.g., the same MPCs are visible.

Regarding the MPC delays for a specific UE position \mathbf{p} , a possible extension of the proposed model would be to consider an additional delay error term $e_{k,m}^{(j)}$ in the computation according to

$$c\tau_{k,m}^{(j)} = \|\mathbf{a}_{k,m}^{(j)} - \mathbf{p}\| + e_{k,m}^{(j)} \quad (4.2)$$

to account for small local variations in the actual reflection point.

4.1.2 Stochastic Model

In the RW context, deterministic models need to take into account not only the geographic and electromagnetic characteristics of the relevant environment, but also the spherical wave front and spatially non-stationary characteristics as a result of near-field propagation. Despite their high accuracy, the large amount of computational effort needed for modeling site-specific geometric features makes deterministic models prohibitive in many cases. For applications like system design and analysis, statistical description of the channel is needed, rather than the exact impulse response at a specific location or time. Stochastic channel models provide the probability density functions (PDFs) of channel impulses or equivalent functions over the area of interest, and normally have much lower computational demand than deterministic models. In practice, deterministic and stochastic models are often combined to balance accuracy and efficiency. For instance, in the channel model (2.2), specular MPCs are modeled deterministically based on the geometric environment information, while the DM and measurement noise are described by stochastic models.

In general, there are two types of stochastic models, namely, correlation-based stochastic models (CBSMs) and geometry-based stochastic models (GBSMs). For CBSMs, e.g., Rayleigh fading channel model, correlation degree is purely based on the spatial or temporal channel correlation factors which are typically obtained from extensive measurement campaigns. CBSMs provide a low-complex and mathematically tractable way for simple system simulating and performance analyzing, but they hardly capture any specific environment features. GBSMs, on the other hand, take account of specific propagation geometry information, such as the spatial stochastic distributions of effective scatterers around UEs or BS and antenna array configurations. These geometry information further results in correlation degree between antennas. In comparison, GBSMs is preferred in terms of accuracy and flexibility.

GBSMs require appropriate scatterer spatial distributions that essentially reflect the physical truth of the propagation environment. If the BS is unobstructed, *one-ring* distribution of scatterers, e.g.,

uniform or Gaussian, around the UEs can be applied. Otherwise, *two-ring* distribution where two clusters of scatterers placed around the BS and UE respectively would be more proper. Note that the autocorrelation function (ACF) of the stochastic processes modeling the visible scatterer clusters at the BS and UE sides respectively are often assumed to be separable especially when the clusters are sufficiently separated from each other.

The distribution of MPC-VR and cluster-VR amplitudes is also a crucial component for RW GB-SMs. In Section. 3, the spatial non-stationary amplitude distribution due to the near-field propagation is clearly shown with the presented measurements. For RW, the amplitude distribution within each VR and the variations over the RW should both be considered. It has been shown in [12] that a proper amplitude model could help to decorrelated the channels to closely-located UEs.

In dynamic scenarios, e.g., the dynamic RW measurement environment in Section. 3.2.1, we observed that different RW portions do not necessarily observe the same set of active MPCs or scatterers, and their VRs can also be time-variant. To incorporate the dynamic characteristics of clusters and scatterers, their respective death-birth processes should be modeled, where the Poisson point/cluster processes are often applied in classic models [12, 16].

In general, one should follow the following steps to build a RW CBSM: (i) determine the number of scatterer clusters and their spatial distributions; (ii) determine the VRs of clusters and probably also their variations given dynamic environment; (iii) determine the path loss to each array element; (iv) generate channel coefficients.

This section summarize a few crucial aspects of the stochastic modeling of RW channels. Of course, there are more statistical characteristics that can be further analyzed from the measurements and considered in the stochastic models, such as the impact of different array configurations, empirical MPC and cluster lifetimes and etc. We leave it for future work.

4.2 Considerations for Applications

This section gives an overview of the how the discussed signal, system and channel model can be applied to various aspects of the RW infrastructure. With reflectarrays being closely related to the RW concept, a straightforward extension or modification of the model is given. Regarding positioning, the subarray based approach employed in the channel analysis is used to describe the possibility of simplifying the model to locally stationary channels that allow a direct application of channel estimation algorithms.

4.2.1 Reflectarrays

[TW: update with citations] The application of reflectarrays to various fields wireless communications is a popular field in the research community [1, 29], dealing with channel modeling [35], communication performance [8, 19] or positioning accuracy [18, 20]. While reflectarrays are also commonly referred to as large intelligent surface (LIS) or reflective intelligent surface (RIS), the fundamental modes of operation are similar, with the devices receiving signals, which are re-transmitted in a steered direction, usually by means of passive switching networks that modify the phase of the incoming signals.

Regarding the application to RW, the proposed model is directly applicable to incorporate reflectarrays in the system. Common models used for reflectarrays (RAs), LIS or reflective intelligent

surface (RIS) are similar to the scattering model that is used to model the DM in a stochastic fashion. By selecting deterministic scatterer locations that resemble the locations of the RA elements, the matrix $\Sigma^{(\text{sc})}(f)$ containing the RCSs or the scatterers turns into the phase shift matrix $\Sigma^{(\text{sc})}(f) \rightarrow \Phi^{(\text{ra})}(f)$ of a RA. This matrix is then used to steer the reflection into the desired direction. A model of this form is used in [7] to analyze the effect of the geometry of a RIS on the communication performance.

4.2.2 Communication

Communication often relies on the knowledge of channel state information (CSI), for example by employing MRT to achieve optimum performance [34]. Especially the inclusion of visibility regions and the analysis of shadowing and signal blockage in models is important for developing robust algorithms to ensure meeting the requirements under realistic channel conditions. Simulations can be performed based on a model calibrated with the measured data to target specific scenarios. The channel model then provides a framework to generate realistic channels including spatially consistent multipath propagation while also including channel randomness when using the DM. In the case of necessary modification to account for new channel conditions, the described deterministic-stochastic channel model allows for an easy trade-off between the two parts.

4.2.3 Positioning

Positioning applications exploit the geometry relation between the received signal and the UE location to estimate from these signals. Starting from an ultrawideband signal model, the received signal $\mathbf{y}_m^{(u)}$ for subarray s and (sub)array element $u \in 1, \dots, U_s$ is defined as

$$\mathbf{y}_u^{(s)} = \sum_k \mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{u,k}^{(s)}) \alpha_{u,k}^{(s)} + \mathbf{n}_u^{(s)} \quad (4.3)$$

considering the spherical wave propagation along a suitably large array as well as the corresponding effects on array element pattern, amplitude and phases in the channel vector $\mathbf{h}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{u,k}^{(s)})$ (according to (2.3) or (2.5)). Omitting the index k for different MPCs, the MPC amplitude is defined as

$$\alpha_u^{(s)} \propto \frac{\gamma}{d_u^{(s)}} b(\mathbf{v}_u^{(s)}) f_u^{(s)} \quad (4.4)$$

where $\gamma \in \mathbb{C}$ is the corresponding source amplitude. The limited visibility of MPCs due to the large physical size of the array is regulated by the visibility function $f_{k,u}^{(s)} = f(\mathbf{a}_k, \mathbf{p}_u^{(s)})$ for a source at some location \mathbf{a}_k . Note that this function depends on the position of each array element and the source and incorporates the effect of a limited spatial extent of reflecting surfaces. In addition, it can be of interest to add the random deviations of the actual delay per MPC described at the beginning of this section, to account for random scattering and non-ideal specular reflection due to surface roughness [26].

4.2.4 Environment Learning and Sensing

For environment learning, it is expected that one can rely on a similar model as used for positioning, i.e., containing multiple specular components as denoted in (4.3) and the corresponding

amplitude model when targeting a parametric-geometric environment model. It is furthermore possible to perform passive sensing of the environment based on the proposed model, by developing algorithms to estimate the statistics of the distribution of scatterers. Furthermore, the physically accurate MPC model allows to quantify the contribution of each MPC towards, e.g., the achievable maximum channel capacity or transmitted power. The inclusion of the MPC visibility regions allows to develop algorithms that can cope with this non-stationarity of the channel. Additionally, a simple SNR map can be learned to quantify the link-quality in a non-parametric fashion, with simulated data using the described model aiding in the algorithm development.

4.2.5 Wireless Power Transfer

For modeling WPT, the REINDEER consortium has put particular emphasis on modeling the signal amplitudes $\alpha_{k,m}^{(j)}$ in a physically correct manner. Consequently, the proportionality in (4.1) will turn into an equality. We would like to refer the reader to the REINDEER deliverable D4.1 [2] for a detailed explanation of the model along with validating synthetic aperture measurements. In fact, a close comparison of (2.3) with the specular multipath component (SMC) model D4.1 [2, Sec. 2.1.1, (2.3)] shows, unveils the similarities of the models:

The antenna patterns $\mathbf{b}_m^{(\text{rx})}(\varphi_{k,m}^{(\text{rx})}, \vartheta_{k,m}^{(\text{rx})})^\top$ and $\mathbf{b}_\ell^{(\text{tx})}(\varphi_{k,\ell}^{(\text{tx})}, \vartheta_{k,\ell}^{(\text{tx})})$ can be thought of as the antenna gain patterns for *amplitudes*, i.e., the complex-valued gains with magnitudes $\sqrt{G_t}$ and $\sqrt{G_r}$ in [2], lumped together with the polarization unit vectors of the antennas ($\boldsymbol{\rho}_t$ and $\boldsymbol{\rho}_r$ in [2]). The amplitude matrix $\mathbf{A}_{k,m}(f)$ may be constructed to accommodate the power spread of spherical waves originating from a transmit antenna, the size of a receiving aperture, losses due to reflections, and rotations of wave polarization due to reflections i.e., $\frac{1}{\sqrt{4\pi}d_{k,\ell}} \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{4\pi}} g_{\text{SMC},k} \mathbf{R}_{k,\ell}$ in [2]. Under these circumstances, the proportionality in (4.1) can be replaced by an equality and the channel matrix \mathbf{H}_k models the propagation of power wave amplitudes in a physically correct manner. The total received power is then

$$P_{\text{rx}}(f) = \|\mathbf{y}(f)\|^2 = \left\| \sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{H}_k(f) \mathbf{w}(f) \right\|^2 P_{\text{tx}} \quad (4.5)$$

with $\mathbf{w}(f)$ as the precoding weight vector and \mathbf{b}_m denoting the complex-valued amplitudes received by the M receiving antennas.

4.2.6 Federations

With federations being an important feature of RW, the use of an MPC-based model allows to directly infer information about the link level, the number of components or simply the received energy or transferred power. This can be achieved based on simulations using the proposed signal model, analyzing specific environments regarding the optimal distribution of CSPs to improve the coverage, minimize latency for time critical communication applications or other cost functions. To obtain the required simulation parameters, the model requires calibration with measurements. When forming federations, the subarray approach used in the analysis of the measurement by performing channel estimation allows to introduce feedback-loop between the federation anchor (FA) and CSPs to increase the system flexibility and help in the federation setup procedure. Positioning and environment learning algorithms can request resources from FAs to achieve use case specific requirements, and pass on estimated CSI to the FAs for further processing.

4.3 Considerations for Use Cases

The use cases that were defined in D1.1 [11], belonging to four application domains that are seen as the main fields of innovation for REINDEER, are all envisioned to rely on the large aperture of the overall RW infrastructure. Often, these use cases rely on a combination of the applications discussed in Section 4.2 and need to deliver high levels of, e.g., positioning accuracy, communication latency for a large number of devices simultaneously [10]. With the distribution of UEs throughout an environment exhibiting large- and small-scale characteristics, it is important to rely on models that can accurately represent them, to develop efficient algorithms. While the introduction of deterministic components related to a specific environment geometry most certainly increases the model complexity, it will nonetheless allow to capture environment specific effects. Regarding different network topologies that were presented [10], environment specific effects contained in these deterministic components can also help in the evaluation of suitable topologies. We envision that the investigated deterministic-stochastic model will be the key to achieve this, while remaining flexible to allow covering of unforeseen challenges that might arise in future applications.

4.4 Considerations for Device Classes

Different device classes that are envisioned to be part of a RW system were described in [11]. With the proposed channel model based on environment specific propagation characteristic (that are independent of the device class), it can be assumed that due to different computation capabilities of devices, any processing requiring the use of some form of model should be adapted to the device. For example assuming passive scattering devices, a simple model including visibility along the RW can be used at the infrastructure side for parametric channel estimation, where sufficient computational power is available. For wake up of energy neutral devices (ENDs) the described visibility model of MPCs can be exploited to optimize the distribution of available power into different beams, exploiting knowledge of an available parametric environment model. Assuming that no parametric model is of interest, e.g., for low power backscatter devices, knowledge of the underlying propagation conditions outlined in the measurement analysis can be used to understand specific effects and develop counter strategies.

Chapter 5

Summary

This deliverable reports on the work performed for task T1.2 focusing on radio channel measurement, characterization and modelling for RW. To study channel characteristics of RW in real indoor environments, several measurement campaigns were conducted in Lund and Graz. We used various measurement settings in terms of geometric configurations of array and UEs, static/dynamic environments, LoS/NLoS propagation conditions and signal bandwidth, etc, to simulate different RW use cases that are defined in deliverable D1.1.

RW in the form of large scale antenna arrays can be essentially viewed as a scaled-up version of conventional massive MIMO systems. However, measurements results exhibit several key differences of RW's channel characteristics from massive MIMO systems. For RW user cases, UEs are typically located within the Rayleigh distance of the receiving array, therefore narrowband and plane wave assumptions are no longer fulfilled over the array as shown in the visualization of UWB signals, which poses additional challenges for the development of efficient channel estimation algorithms. Different array portions of the RW view differently on the propagation environment which leads to variations on the channel characteristics along the RW. It is firstly observed that the overall received power intensity is non-uniform across the LSA. If we further zoom into individual propagation components, variation on their power intensities and visibilities across the LSA are also clearly demonstrated with the estimation results of super-resolution algorithm SBL. Same as the deterministic part of the channel. Fading statistics also becomes non-wide sense stationary for RW. Specifically, SSF distributions vary over subarrays with different received power intensity. Shadow fading from environment object and human body yields notably different statistics. These non-stationary properties can be potentially exploited to reduce the computational complexity by processing only the most informative measurements, e.g., measurements from power-concentrated subarrays. Furthermore, decentralized and scalable hardware architectures and algorithms are more and more adopted for large scale arrays, where signal processing is performed locally at each subarray and then locate estimates are fused at the central processing unit. To enhance algorithm performance, the deterministic and stochastic channel characteristic discussed above should be essentially considered, but with different emphasis for different applications.

Apart from the observations on the channel properties, we also performed preliminary investigation on the potential of using RW for super-resolution parametric channel estimation, user spatial separability and wireless power transmission. It shows that the superior spatial resolution of RW together with wideband or even UWB signals enables high accurate parametric estimation of MPCs that are associated to geometric propagation environment. Besides, the estimated chan-

nel condition number and results from MRT demonstrate excellent spatial separability of closely located UEs and potential on using RW for WPT even under NLoS propagation conditions with diffracted signals only.

We believe that the detailed and comprehensive study on RW channel characteristics based on real radio measurements and novel perspectives of RW channel modeling provided in this deliverable will be of broad interest to various communities.

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